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Master Thesis

Spatial-Temporal Optimisation for Green Hydrogen Production: A Case Study of Laos

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Abstract

The Government of Laos seeks to expand its hydropower capacity, aiming to boost the economy by leveraging its abundant resources. However, the national energy company faces challenges such as profitability and limited negotiation ability due to international power projects. For sustainable growth, it is necessary to advance the local industry and diversify beyond electricity exports, which have proven to be a loss for Laos. A viable strategy involves producing green hydrogen via electrolysis, using Laos's abundant water resources and renewable generation potential. Spatial-temporal optimisation is used to identify the least-cost sites for green hydrogen production by partitioning the country into hexagonal units, as defined in the GeoH2 model. In each hexagon, an algorithm identifies suitable areas for PV panels and wind turbines. Subsequently, these identified sites contribute to the optimisation of the power system to meet the annual urea demand of Laos while minimising the overall system cost and the Levelised Cost of Hydrogen (LCOH). The model has been tailored to Laos, incorporating the integration of hydropower with a unique hydraulic head calculation along with a comprehensive selection of potential sites suitable for renewable energy sources based on slope. Laos can produce green hydrogen at an LCOH of 2.18 \$/kg by 2030, positioning it as a competitive participant on the international market. This depends highly on the availability of hydropower, but a production output of almost 1 million tons is achievable post-2030.

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Acronyms

AOI	area of interest
ASEAN	Association of Southeast Asian Nations
BESS	battery energy storage systems
CAPEX	capital expenditures
CCS	carbon capture and storage
COD	commercial operating date
CRF	capital recovery factor
CRS	coordinate reference System
DEM	digital elevation model
EdL	Electricité du Laos
EdL-Gen	Electricite du Lao Generation Public Company
EU	European Union
FAO	Food and Agriculture Organisation of the United Nations
GDP	gross domestic product
HHV	higher heating value
IEA	International Energy Agency
IPP	independent power producers
IQR	interquartile range
IRA	Inflation Reduction Act
LCOH	Levelised Cost of Hydrogen
LHV	lower heating value
LMIC	low- and middle-income countries
LOHC	Liquid organic hydrogen carriers
MAE	mean absolute error
MCDM	multi-criteria decision-making
MEM	Ministry of Energy and Mines
MOU	Memorandum of Understanding
MW	megawatt
PEM	Polymer Electrolyte Membrane
PV	photovoltaic
PyPSA	Python for Power System Analysis
RES	renewable energy sources
SMR	Steam Methane Reforming
STD	standard deviation
US	United States
WACC	weighted average cost of capital

1 Introduction

Addressing climate change presents numerous challenges, and although renewable energy sources offer a solution to decarbonising the power grid, it has been more challenging to decarbonise energy-intensive sectors [1]. Hydrogen has multiple uses in such industries and is currently mainly produced with Steam Methane Reforming (SMR), a high carbon-emitting process [2], [3]. Green hydrogen presents a viable substitute, encompassing processes such as hydrogen electrolysis, biomass gasification, and solar water splitting, among others [4].

A promising developing country concerning renewable energy sources (RES) is the Lao People's Democratic Republic (Lao PDR or Laos) in the centre of South East Asia. The country has substantial hydroelectric resources and is expected to expand this capacity. Furthermore, it has a high potential for solar photovoltaic (PV) generation [5]. Most of the electricity generated is currently exported to neighbouring countries, but it is also attractive for green hydrogen [6]. Recent developments and the interest of the Lao PDR government in investing in hydrogen and ammonia production show that it is a "hot" topic to produce hydrogen locally [7], [8]. Additionally, there is international interest in Laos, as demonstrated by a recent collaboration with Australia to explore the possibilities of a domestic hydrogen sector [9]. Laos has no significant industry that requires hydrogen, but the agricultural sector consumes large amounts of fertiliser and the production of hydrogen-based fertilisers, such as urea, is in high demand. A domestic production could provide multiple benefits to Laos's economy.

The International Energy Agency (IEA) has a global LCOH map highlighting low-cost areas. This is based on capacity factors for solar PV and onshore wind generation and is calculated with an estimated weighted average cost of capital (WACC) of 6%. Figure 1 displays the LCOH map of South East Asia along with the boundaries of Laos. It is particularly noteworthy that the northern region of Laos could have exceptionally low production expenses. However, the vast hydroelectric capacity is not reflected in the LCOH model of the IEA, and for detailed examination, the granularity must be higher. Moreover, research into the potential for hydrogen in Laos is constrained by the recent emergence of the subject in Laos and a lack of data.

Figure 1: South East Asia's Levelised Cost of Hydrogen Potential. Cutout from the IEA map [10].

This emphasises the need for a model with higher granularity to make better strategic decisions about the location and capacity of production sites. Specifically, this includes the inclusion of local hydropower, transmission lines, and demand. Developing such a model requires a deep understanding of hydrogen production. Furthermore, it is essential to project the demand for domestic fertilisers to provide guidance on the local capacity required to meet this demand.

1.1 Background

The energy sector already has an incredible influence on the economy of Laos, and the Government of Laos plans to expand this [11]. Through the vast availability of hydropower in Laos and an ideal position to export this electricity, it is reasonable to expand this capacity and make it a cornerstone of their economy. However, to this point, Electricité du Laos (EdL) has yet to achieve profitability from established export agreements, and, notably, the independent power producers (IPP)s of the surrounding countries have the potential to undermine the negotiation capabilities of Laos. Additionally, there needs to be more certainty about the benefits for local communities of building hydroelectric dams. This is further emphasised by the fact that hydropower has one of the shortest life cycles in terms of job creation, particularly in operation and maintenance [12]. These points justify advancing the local industry in Laos and not relying solely on exporting electricity, but on producing subsequent products with electricity.

One of these products could be hydrogen through hydrogen electrolysis. The abundance of water in the Mekong and the production of electricity through hydropower make Laos an ideal location for the production of green hydrogen. In addition, hydrogen production can generate higher margins than selling electricity. This could already be used as an export product; otherwise, it acts as an input for urea production. Urea is an energy-intensive fertiliser currently entirely imported and is often produced using grey hydrogen, which is also energy-intensive. From this perspective, two objectives can be achieved: to boost the domestic industry and to reduce the carbon footprint of a necessary commodity.

Through fertiliser production, Laos will also be independent of fluctuations in the global market. This was an issue at the beginning of 2022, as fertiliser prices rose due to the Russian invasion of Ukraine. As Laos has high inflation rates and is at a disadvantage if goods are traded in US dollars, this could stabilise its domestic market. Although the share of the agricultural industry has decreased in recent years, more than 50% of Laos population is still active in that sector and will remain so in the future. This is supported by the increase in the Crop Production Index of the World Bank and the overall increase in the use of fertilisers in Laos, according to the United Nations, in recent years. The construction of hydrogen or even subsequent urea production plants is associated with a high initial capital cost, placing additional pressure on Laos existing debt. However, if the benefits of such a plant are compared to those of an additional hydropower plant, constructing a chemical plant seems to provide a higher welfare. Selecting the optimal and least-cost site is a high priority in such circumstances.

1.2 Objective

The aim of this thesis is to determine the most cost-effective hydrogen production locations within Laos, based on the domestic urea demand. For conservative and realistic LCOH values, it is vital to adapt the GeoH2 model specifically for Laos. This adaptation requires the incorporation of hydropower, given the extensive availability in Laos. In addition, mountainous terrain and protected areas must be considered for the development of renewable energy. The model output will be analysed across the temporal, spatial, and climate impact dimensions. The temporal analysis will estimate the future costs of hydrogen production and the potential spatial fluctuations. In the spatial analysis, domestic demand will be broken down into smaller regions to see the dependence of changed demand centres. The climate impact dimension is highly relevant to hydropower, as climate change induces greater variability in capacity factors. Here, the actual capacity factors for hydropower plants in a dry and wet year are compared and the elasticity of LCOH is shown. This will give a comprehensive assessment of the spatial aspect for hydrogen production in Laos.

2 Literature Review

2.1 Hydrogen and Fertiliser

Hydrogen consists of a single proton and electron, and is the simplest and most abundant element in the cosmos [13]. Next to that, hydrogen has the highest energy density of any fuel and a higher heating value (HHV) of 144 MJ / kg and a lower heating value (LHV) of 120 MJ/kg [13]. This makes it attractive for use as an energy supply or for multiple end-use applications¹.

In recent years, multiple strategies and regulations have been implemented that highlight the relevance of hydrogen today and in the future. The European Hydrogen Strategy aims to develop a clean hydrogen production capacity for the generation of 10 million tons in the European Union (EU) by 2030, and includes investments by member states with a total of 9.3 billion euros that are attributed only to clean hydrogen production in the EU [14]. This is significant since current production without considering clean hydrogen is 10 million tons in the EU [14]. In the United States (US), the Inflation Reduction Act (IRA) had a significant influence on the construction of new clean hydrogen plants and was the largest subsidy act worldwide. In 2020, the US Department of Energy published a strategy to enable low carbon hydrogen production [3]. This aligns with the prediction for clean hydrogen. In 2018, more than 95% of hydrogen was produced from fossil fuels, and approximately 90 million tons of grey hydrogen are consumed annually worldwide [15], [16]. The demand for clean hydrogen is estimated to increase to between 125 and 585 million tons by 2050, and clean hydrogen could account for more than 70% of the total demand [16]. A report from McKinsey & Co. anticipates that after 2025, most of the upcoming hydrogen facilities will generate clean hydrogen [16].

The increase in demand for hydrogen, especially clean hydrogen, comes from the decarbonisation efforts of energy-intensive industries. The use of hydrogen to decarbonise energy-intensive industries, such as steel and fertiliser production, is the most significant use case and remains highly relevant [2]. Another possibility is the usage of hydrogen as an intermediate storage to balance the fluctuation of renewable energy sources. The estimated current round-trip efficiency of hydrogen, which includes conversion from electricity to hydrogen and back to electricity, is between 21 and 29%, potentially exceeding 40% in the future [17]. However, this low efficiency remains a major disadvantage as a storage technology for energy provision. For this reason, this option has not been considered further.

The costs of green hydrogen production differ between countries and depend on the availability of renewable energy sources. Consequently, countries that possess a significant proportion of RES are particularly attractive for the production of green hydrogen. Within the scope of low- and middle-income countries (LMIC), the domestic industry has a notable benefit from the generation of green hydrogen and the manufacture of fertilisers, since agriculture is more dependent on LMIC [18]. In addition, they achieve multiple benefits compared to developed countries in the north. In the following, an overview of the production of hydrogen and fertilisers is provided and placed in the context of LMIC.

2.1.1 Hydrogen and Fertiliser Production

There exist multiple hydrogen production processes: thermochemical, electrolytic, direct solar water splitting, and biological processes. Comprehensive descriptions of the different chemical production processes are provided in Appendix A. Here, only electrolysis is considered in combination with renewable energy sources, as the focus is on the production of low-carbon hydrogen

¹Hydrogen is also the reason the Earth exists. Stars are formed from two extremely cold collapsing hydrogen clouds. As they gain density and weight, they trigger nuclear fusion, and over billions of years, this process gives rise to planets, people, and other stuff.

Figure 2: The unit process of urea manufacturing with electrolysis and required energy input. Own illustration based on [24], [26]–[28].

and urea production. Fertiliser manufacturing requires a significant amount of energy and is often based on the process of natural gas or coal gasification. The global production of synthetic fertilisers emits more emissions than combined emissions from aviation and shipping [19]. Therefore, the reduction of carbon emissions in fertiliser manufacturing plays a crucial role in mitigating climate change, which can be achieved by making hydrogen production more sustainable [20]. As part of nitrogen fertilisers, urea is one of the most widely used fertilisers [21], [22]. Here, the emphasis will be exclusively on urea, particularly because of its foundation on hydrogen. It is manufactured using ammonia, which is derived from hydrogen:

Hydrogen is typically generated by steam methane reforming, and the captured CO_2 is then used in the urea production process.

The whole urea production process is explained in the following, based on Milani et al. [23]. The urea synthesis production process starts with hydrogen production, where H_2O and CH_4 are used as input for steam reforming reactors. With heat, this transforms into CO , N_2 , and H_2 , which are used as input for the water-gas shift reactor. Here, H_2O is added again and results in CO , CO_2 , N_2 and H_2 . CO_2 has to be removed and is used as input in the urea production step. Methanation results in N_2 and H_2 only. This is used in the urea synthesis. It starts with a compressor, cooling and is transformed through the Haber-Bosch process to NH_3 , ammonia. Urea synthesis requires NH_3 and CO_2 and transforms it into NH_4 and H_2NCO_2 . A distillation tower divides it into NH_2 and $2CO_2$, eventually leading to urea.

Decarbonisation of urea production requires the use of green hydrogen for ammonia synthesis and sustainable electricity for heating operations [23]. When electrolysis is used, a separate CO_2 source is needed, a challenge not present in biomass-derived hydrogen generation. In Figure 2, the unit process of urea is visible for an electrolysis-based process. Hydrogen electrolysis is assumed to require 33 kWh / kg, which is equal to 0.1188 GJ [24]. Therefore, 11.88 GJ are required for 100 kg of hydrogen. Ammonia contains 17.8% hydrogen, and around 100 kg of hydrogen result in 570 kg of ammonia [25]. Ammonia production requires 39.8 GJ/tonne, resulting in 22.689 GJ for 570 kg of ammonia, which are required as input for urea production [26]. Urea production requires 2.8 GJ/tonne. Consequently, the total unit process of urea requires 37.3 GJ/tonne.

Hydrogen production based on biomass gasification is shown in Figure 3, based on [27]–[29]. The difference from the electrolysis-based process is the availability of CO_2 from biomass, making a carbon capture and storage (CCS) plant obsolete. The hydrogen yield is assumed to be 0.1 kg of hydrogen per kg of biomass, corresponding to a conversion efficiency of 67% based on a higher

Figure 3: The unit process of urea manufacturing with biomass gasification. Own illustration based on [27]–[29].

heating value (HHV) [28]. Therefore, around 1 ton of biomass is required for 1 ton of urea.

2.1.2 Hydrogen and Fertiliser in Low- and Middle-Income Countries

Hydrogen production has significant energy consumption, and for green hydrogen the power is derived from, for example, wind turbines or PV panels, requiring substantial space to meet the demand. Through a lower yield of renewables in the north compared to countries in the south, green hydrogen production has a competitive advantage. An argument is the increase in solar irradiance in the south, which directly influences the performance of PV panels [5]. Consequently, the cost of green hydrogen is cheaper in areas with high renewable yields and examples are Oman, the south of Africa, or the south of America [18]. Interestingly, it is often more beneficial to have optimal mixed conditions for wind and PV power generation than places with exceptionally favourable conditions for wind or PV alone individually [30]. This is due to the reliable and constant electricity demand for hydrogen production and low tolerance to fluctuations. The same holds for the production of ammonia and urea. In contrast to PV and wind, hydropower could provide such reliable electricity on its own. Transporting hydrogen costs only a fraction of the total costs, and shipping hydrogen, even over long distances, can be cost-competitive with locally produced hydrogen [18]. Because of this, the transport of hydrogen from the south to meet the demand in the north is attractive. If typical risks in LMIC are considered, for example, lower political stability, this increases the cost of investing through higher interest rates [30].

Furthermore, there are potential advantages for LMIC in producing fertilisers domestically to ensure self-sufficiency and reduce vulnerability to price fluctuations. The rise in fertiliser prices due to the Russian invasion of Ukraine has had a swift and substantial impact recently, particularly affecting LMIC [31]. Therefore, local fertiliser production allows LMIC to decrease global market fluctuations.

2.2 Geospatial Analysis

Geospatial analysis models simplify intricate geospatial occurrences, such as urban growth and environmental changes. They play a vital role in decision-making processes such as infrastructure development and emergency response.

In the context of green hydrogen, it is crucial to regard the geospatial component as the required inputs, electricity and water, which must be in proximity to the production site. Taking South Africa as an example, visible in Figure 4, water availability is mainly in the south and far east of the country [32]. Although the transmission grid is located mainly east of the country,

the west of South Africa experiences the highest solar irradiance [33]. The optimal and least-cost production site can be determined by considering all factors influencing the selection. The best way to do this is to use an optimisation model.

2.2.1 Review on Existing Hydrogen Mapping

The identification of least cost hydrogen production sites has been done in multiple papers. A study has been conducted for hydrogen production in Iceland by [34], based on the approach of [35]. More recently, [36] developed a multi-criteria method based on GIS specifically for PV hydrogen production. Similarly, for PV hydrogen production, a multi-criteria decision-making (MCDM) based site selection framework was developed by [37]. The model encompasses elements of the economy, technology, society, and the environment. For hydrogen production based on wind energy, an adapted approach was used by [38]. A least cost model named GeoH2, which uses data from PV and wind generation data, was developed by [39]. It is country-agnostic, but is especially useful for LMIC, as generic data, such as, for example, solar irradiation, wind and weather data, are used, overcoming data availability issues.

Figure 4: Own illustration of transmission grid and water flow in South Africa; created with QGIS based on OpenStreetMap data.

A review of the literature on geospatial infrastructure analysis was carried out by [40], splitting the literature into national, regional and local scale studies. Multiple key weaknesses were identified by [40]: representation of the structure of the transport market, behavioural dynamics, and spatial structure below the national state scale. In particular, the lack of spatial information at the regional and local levels remained a key weakness. For western countries, such as Germany, [41] performed a geospatial analysis of the hydrogen supply chain for Germany, considering different transportation and storage solutions, resulting in specific infrastructure layouts. This could be done due to the high availability of data. For LMIC, this is often a key drawback for deep geospatial analysis.

2.2.2 Review on the GeoH2 Model

The GeoH2 model was developed by [39] and optimises the production of green hydrogen production based on spatial-temporal data for wind and solar generation availability. As a result, hexagons with the lowest cost can be identified as possible locations for production. Hexagons have only one distance between the centre and all neighbours, making them ideal for geospatial analysis. The hexagons were implemented based on Uber’s hexagonal hierarchical spatial index, called H3. This model was used in [42] for a case study in Kenya and successfully identified the areas with the lowest cost.

The GeoH2 model is ideally suited to look at LMIC countries with low data availability and provides the basis for a least-cost production site analysis. With a focus on Laos, it becomes necessary to incorporate hydropower plants, as their primary source of electricity generation relies on them. Excluding them would result in a significant loss of information. However, the incorporation of hydropower presents several difficulties. The yield of wind and solar energy is derived from input files, which assign a value to each hexagon. Incorporating existing hydropower

sites would only give a value in a specific location, leaving the rest of the hexagons undetermined or at zero. An alternative method involves identifying the ideal locations for hydropower plants and assigning a value to each hexagon based on this optimisation. There are various strategies to determine the most suitable locations, which will be analysed in the development process [43], [44].

2.3 Lao PDR

Evidence suggests that humans have inhabited Laos for almost ten thousand years. Between the fourth and eighth centuries, rural communities, called 'Muang', emerged along the Mekong River and were presumably settled by the Ti tribe of southern China [45]. In the 13th century, the Mongol invasion of China increased migration to Laos [45]. During the 16th century, under King Setthathirath's rule, Laos capital was relocated to Vientiane, which it still is today. It was not until the 17th century that European attention towards the country grew, with notable interest from the Dutch and the East India Company [46]. However, internal division in the 18th century led to Siamese, now known as Thailand, control over much of Laos until the French colonised it in 1893 [45]. Laos remained a French colony until World War II, when Japan occupied the country. After the second world war, Laos gained independence in 1953, but internal conflicts continued [45]. The bombing of North Vietnamese troops in the eastern Laos in 1964 by the US led to further conflict, eventually culminating in the establishment of the Lao PDR People's Democratic Republic in 1975 [45].

Located in Southeast Asia, Laos is the only landlocked country which poses numerous challenges to its economic growth in Southeast Asia. The government is divided into 18 provinces, with Vientiane being its capital [47]. It is surrounded by China, Vietnam, Cambodia, Thailand, and Myanmar. The terrain is mainly mountainous, with forests covering about 47% of the land [48]. Known locally as Nam Khong, the Mekong is the country's longest river, stretching 1,900 km within the borders of Laos and serving as the primary source of water and energy. Significant yearly precipitation and altitude variations in the country provide substantial hydroelectric potential, with 7.2 GW installed today and an additional potential of 23 GW [49], [50]. The current Laotian electricity grid comprises lignite, small shares of wind and solar, but mainly of hydropower [50]. This hydroelectric power generation is set to be the cornerstone of Laos economy in the future [51]. Laos Power Development Plan in 2014 estimated a peak demand of 5,700 MW in 2030, with annual growth of 12% [52].

2.3.1 Economy

In 1986, Laos changed to an open-door economic policy, and since then, the economy has experienced rapid growth [48]. A significant milestone was reached when Laos became a member of the Association of Southeast Asian Nations (ASEAN) in July 1997 [45]. The poverty rate decreased by 18% between 1997 and 2003 to 32% [53]. Furthermore, the economy has consistently transitioned from being predominantly agricultural to a market-based system incorporating various sectors, including services and industry. In 2013, the services sector had a share of 37.9% of total GDP, while the agriculture sector had only 23.5% [48]. This changed further in 2016 when the services sector increased to 48%, the industrial sector to 33% and the agricultural industry was reduced to 19% [50]. It should be noted that 58% of Laos population is still active in the agricultural sector, despite its decreasing share of the gross domestic product (GDP) [54].

The massive increase in its economy is visible through the GDP, as shown in Figure 5, which shows an average growth of 13.7% between 2005 and 2019. In red, phases with a reduction of the GDP are shown. The 1980s were driven by the insurgence between two parties, resulting in

Figure 5: GDP time series of Laos. Own illustration based on World Bank Data [55]

significant economic uncertainty [46]. The coronavirus pandemic in 2020 is also evident, leading to the most substantial decline in over two decades. Considering the inflation corrected GDP, there was still a small growth of 2.3% in 2022, but the effects on the economy were nevertheless negative [56]. Laos remained the third largest economy in Southeast Asia, a status it also maintained in 2017 [50], [56].

Wealth came mainly from resource-driven development initiatives such as hydropower, mining, agricultural business, and infrastructure [57]. Furthermore, tourism and the contribution of overseas labour remittances to household expenditure [58]. This was especially visible in Vientiane through a booming real estate market. However, while new hydroelectric dam projects have been established in rural areas, it is more difficult to detect how this new wealth has benefited local communities [57].

The hydroelectric industry, along with other infrastructure initiatives such as the Lao-China Railway, which cost \$5.9 billion, has significantly increased the state-backed debt of Laos [59]. This, in turn, has increased financial risk and was particularly noticeable during the coronavirus pandemic when Laos was on the verge of bankruptcy [57]. The primary cause was excessive investment in projects that required substantial capital, a situation that could have been prevented as per [57]. According to [57] and [55], the governments of Laos and China, with China being a major investor, should have taken more into account the capacity of Laos to repay its debt and the revenue-generating potential of its investments. Unless substantial changes are made or debt is restructured, the level of debt will continue to be unsustainable, characterised by hefty debt service commitments and escalating requirements for gross financing [55]. The Asian Development Outlook, in its April 2024 edition, forecasted growth in GDP of 4% for both 2024 and 2025, taking into account the impact of high debt and inflation [60]. The main risks for Laos in the next 2 to 3 years, according to an AMRO report, are continued weakness in the bank balance sheets, a rise in global energy prices, increased currency substitution, and most importantly, lower government access to foreign currency financing sources [6]. Climate change and natural disasters pose a significant and ongoing threat [6], [61].

2.3.2 Electricity Sector

Although it has one of the lowest per capita electricity use rates in Southeast Asia, 725 kWh in 2017, the energy intensity of its economy exceeds that of Indonesia, Myanmar, and the Philippines [50]. This is underscored by the fact that hydropower alone generates 15% of Laos export revenue [50]. From 1990 onwards, there has been an intensive development of hydropower capacity to meet the power demand of Laos and its neighbouring nations, and the revenue generated from this greatly contributes to the socio-economic development of Laos [48]. The first hydropower dam, the Nam Ngum Dam, was completed in 1971 [49]. During the Cold War, the development of new hydropower dams was largely stopped in the Mekong area, but since then, many other power projects have followed [49]. Thailand, in particular, has had a significant influence on the progress of these projects. The first Memorandum of Understanding (MOU) between Laos and Thailand was signed in 1993 and supported the development of power projects in Laos by providing up to 1500 MW of electricity to Thailand [62]. A recent agreement saw the power purchase scheme expand to supply 7000 MW of electricity to Thailand by 2020 [62]. Similarly, the Lao government signed MOUs with Vietnam to supply electricity, with the agreed supply increasing from 2000 MW in 1998 to 5000 MW by 2020 [62].

Figure 6: Existing hydropower dams. Own illustration based on data provided by the Lao PDR Government.

However, in the early 2000s, there was a decline in the appeal of hydropower energy, attributed to a decrease in market demand and the persistent economic difficulties of the Asian financial crisis, leading to limited hydropower growth in Laos [49]. The findings of the World Dams Commission on the harmful social and environmental impacts of dams further discouraged major institutions from investing in new dams during this period [63]. Despite these challenges, the World Bank gave its approval in 2005 for the controversial Nam Theun 2 Hydropower Project in central Laos, which was the largest dam in the Mekong River basin at that time [49]. In the 2010s, the development of new hydropower increased again, and in 2019, Laos alone had 61 hydropower dams with a total installed capacity of 7207 MW [49]. Figure 6 shows the capacity and location of these dams, the majority in the north and the south of the country.

Figure 7: Institutional Framework of the power sector in Laos ([64])

As mentioned above, the hydropower sector is instrumental in increasing electricity export revenues and integrating Laos into the global economy. In this context, the MEM is the primary governing body divided into two divisions [64]. First, the Department of Energy Promotion and Development is tasked with developing renewable energy, rural electrification, electricity export, and planning electricity generation, transmission, and distribution. Second, the Department of Energy Policy and Planning is in charge of formulating policies and regulations and supervising both public and private energy providers. The MEM also oversees three business units in the power industry, visible in Figure 8:

- EdL, a utility responsible for electricity generation, transmission, and distribution facilities, and managing electricity import and export [57].
- Lao Holding State Enterprise, the organisation that holds the government's shares in IPP.
- Electrical Construction and Installation Company is the construction collaborator for EdL in their distribution and transmission projects.

EdL specifically plays a vital role in funding hydropower projects, and it is primarily through this that it faces significant financial exposure. Before the creation of the EdL Transmission Company in 2020, it solely managed the transmission and distribution of energy within Laos [57], [64]. It is still the sole buyer of electricity from Electricite du Lao Generation Public Company (EdL-Gen), as visible in Figure 8 [6]. Furthermore, it has a crucial position in energy initiatives, either as a minority partner in overseas funded IPP projects aimed at local or international markets or as a sole investor [57]. This role, in particular, led to substantial debts and an unstable financial situation since neither local nor electrical exports are yet profitable for EdL [50].

Figure 8: Split in domestic and export market [6]

The liabilities of EdL can increase to \$8 billion before it starts to decrease [57]. In 2020, its obligations to pay debt were projected to increase, moving from \$400 million in 2020 to \$800 million in 2023, before the department gradually began decreasing it according to [61]. This projected decrease in EdLs debt commitments was based on the expectation that the duration of the nation’s IPP investors would conclude, resulting in Laos benefiting from enhanced revenue flows due to complete ownership of the dams subsequently [57].

A 2023 report concluded that the electricity sector in Laos showed mixed performance when comparing the export and domestic markets, and details will be presented in the following [6]. The export sector has shown steady results and is expected to positively impact the Laos economy through export and fiscal income in the foreseeable future. In contrast, the domestic sector is plagued by several structural issues detrimental to the Laotian economy. As highlighted above, EdL presents a substantial financial threat, extending its impact to various other sectors of the economy. Furthermore, the separation between the export and domestic markets, as shown in Figure 8, may eventually vanish as IPP assets are set to be handed over to the government once the concession

Figure 9: Power development plan of Laos [50]

agreement ends. If the separation between the export and domestic markets disappears, the sustainability of the growth of Laos electricity sector would increase.

Laos exports most of the electricity, around 75%, to neighbouring countries [6]. In 2019, it had 33 interconnectors with its neighbours: 17 with Thailand, 7 with Vietnam, 4 with China, 2 with Cambodia, and 1 with Myanmar [50]. The MOUs supplied Thailand with 9 GW, Vietnam with 5 GW, Cambodia with 1.5 GW, and up to 500 MW with Myanmar [50]. This again highlights the importance of Thailand in Laos electricity sector. These interconnections are visible in Figure 9; black dotted lines show the existing transmission lines, and the red dotted lines show the planned transmission lines [50]. A total of 25 additional transmission lines were projected to be established by 2025; however, the current status of this plan remains uncertain.

	2022	2025	2030	2040
Electricity Demand GWh	9427.0075	11719.009	15464.012	30321.118
Hourly Demand MW	1076.1424	1337.7865	1765.2982	3461.3148
Total Capacity MW	9623	11086.14	13326.34	16457.34
Ratio Total %	89%	88%	87%	79%
Domestic Capacity MW	3943.086	4195.086	4423.086	5328.086
Ratio Domestic %	73%	68%	60%	35%

Table 1: Electricity demand and hydropower generation capacity over time (MEM)

In Table 1, the projected electricity demand for 2022 to 2040 is illustrated. Subsequently, the ratio of the hourly electricity consumption to the total hydropower capacity is calculated, thereby defining the available hydropower capacity after domestic demand. This calculation is extended to domestic capacity, where the ratio is predictably smaller due to the exclusion of IPP capacity. In this context, electricity is transmitted directly to adjacent countries, making it inaccessible for domestic use in Laos.

		Dry Season	Wet Season
Dry Year	2019	0.22917	0.35858
	2020	0.23251	0.40721
	2021	0.23772	0.44881
Wet Year	2022	0.27790	0.52631
	2023	0.27950	0.45035

Table 2: Annual hydropower capacity factors splitted by dry and wet season (MEM)

Table 2 visualises the seasonal differences between the years 2019 to 2023, which can have massive impacts on the generation of electricity from hydropower. Especially 2019, is disting due to its low capacity factor and can be considered a relatively dry year. In contrast, 2022 has high capacity factors. With climate change, the differences between dry and wet years are expected to increase, which can have a profound impact on the electricity system and future planning of electricity generation [65]. Therefore, this is of considerable significance for hydropower.

2.3.3 Hydrogen and Fertiliser in Lao PDR

At present, Laos does not produce hydrogen, but there is a strategic roadmap for South East Asia to encourage the growth of a hydrogen industry [66]. Although multiple Asian countries have

already developed hydrogen strategies, Laos is not one of them [67]. However, Laos is currently conducting feasibility studies, and there are multiple goals to build a hydrogen industry with international support [7]–[9].

In terms of fertiliser, there is anticipation for an increase in production capacity, since Laos has only produced approximately 30% of the 2 million tonnes consumed each year and is eager to strengthen its domestic production; the main type of fertiliser produced in Laos is organic [68]. The World Bank and the Food and Agriculture Organisation of the United Nations (FAO) provide numbers for recent years. Data on the quantity and input of fertilisers per unit of agricultural land are taken from [69], while the food production index, data on agricultural land and forest area are derived from [70]. The food production index shows the relative level of the total volume of agricultural production each year, benchmarked against the reference period of 2014-2016. The graph clearly shows a steady increase in the use of fertilisers, to the same extent as the food production index, in Laos, resulting in an excess of 60,000 tonnes in 2019.

The worldwide need for fertilisers is expected to expand to meet an increasing population. In particular, urea, the leading player in the nitrogen fertiliser market, will continue to be important in South Asian nations [71]. In 2016, South Asian countries were net importers of urea and had already decided to increase domestic production capacity [71]. It can be contended that it would also be attractive for Laos to develop its urea production capabilities.

3 Methodology

The research employs the GeoH2 model, developed by Halloran, Leonard, Salmon, *et al.* [39], a spatial optimisation tool that minimises the costs of green hydrogen production, storage, and transport. The model identifies the least cost locations for green hydrogen production by integrating spatial data on wind and solar availability. Through that, an assessment of the economic feasibility of national green hydrogen production can be made, facilitating more informed decision-making. Figure 10, gives an overview of the different inputs and variables. Electricity generation feeds directly into hydrogen production. The hydrogen storage is optimised in size and usage with options of compressed storage (500 bar), liquid hydrogen (LH2), LOHC, and ammonia. Transport options are either trucking or pipeline. The form of the demand has to be set in advance. The process is divided into two repositories: [GeoH2-data-prep](#) and [GeoH2-master](#). This is described in more detail by Halloran, Leonard, Salmon, *et al.* [39] and Müller, Leonard, Trotter, *et al.* [42], but a brief description will be given here.

Figure 10: Process steps in GeoH2 model with additions shown in green. Own illustration.

The initial repository is responsible for preparing the data and creating a preliminary hexagon file that includes the essential information needed for the optimisation, which is carried out in the subsequent GeoH2-master repository. GeoH2-data-prep involves preprocessing spatial data, including country boundaries, waterways, water bodies, roads, and land cover classifications. This is required to 1) constrain land availability for renewable energy infrastructure and 2) calculate costs associated with transport and water supply. The open source libraries [GLAES](#), by Ryberg, Robinius, and Stolten [72], and [SPIDER](#) are used to limit land availability for wind and solar energy installations and to produce H3 hexagons, as mentioned in [39]. Land availability directly influences how many wind turbines and solar farms can be placed within a hexagon, influencing the capacity. The output is a geojson file with hexagons layered above the given area of interest (AOI). The optimisation process is conducted within the GeoH2-master repository across several Python files in the following sequence:

1. `assign_country.py`: The interest rate is assigned to each hexagon for the different technologies.
2. `get_weather_data.py`: Historical weather data are used to determine wind and solar potential using the ERA-5 dataset via [Atlite](#) [73], [74].
3. `optimize_transport_and_conversion.py`: Determines the most cost-efficient hydrogen transportation method to the closest demand center.

4. `optimize_hydrogen_plant.py`: Calculate the demand and optimise the size of the components of green hydrogen plants based on the renewable potential, the hydrogen demand, and the country parameters.
5. `water_cost.py`: Costs associated with water for hydrogen production in each hexagonal area.
6. `total_hydrogen_cost.py`: Compiles all preceding data to determine the most cost-effective hydrogen.
7. `costs_by_component.py`: Divides LCOH into cost components associated with generation, production, and conversion.
8. `map_cost.py`: This script provides a visual representation of the hydrogen cost distribution for every demand center.

The specifications are given across multiple parameter files to define the costs for each element. In the following, only the `optimize_hydrogen_plant.py` file will be further analysed. After preprocessing and preparing the required data for transport cost calculations in the previous files, in this file the actual hydrogen plant is optimised. This occurs in conjunction with an optimisation of the power system, which is performed with `PyPSA`; Python for Power System Analysis (PyPSA) [75]. Figure 10 illustrates the parameters from both the supply and demand perspectives, and the green boxes represent the additions made in this study. The specific details of the final demand are predetermined by the parameter files. From the generation side, solar and wind capacity are optimised as well as sizing the electrolyzer capacity. The size of the electrolyzer must meet the demand, and the function `demand_schedule()` calculates the hourly demand. The hourly capacity factor for wind and solar is calculated with cutouts from Atlite [74]. These provide weather data on an annual level down to hourly capacity factors. A turbine and panel type has to be selected, and for solar the orientation. The adapted GeoH2 repository used in this study can be found [here](#).

3.1 Advancing Spatial Data Preparation and Filtering

In this research two new preprocessing steps were developed to make the model more tailored for the case study of Laos. Guaranteeing that the created hexagons fully cover the AOI is a valuable addition to the SPIDER repository and guarantees that hydropower plants close to the border of Laos are included properly. An exclusion of areas based on a slope threshold was already implemented in other papers, for solar farms, by Elboshy, Alwetaishi, M. H. Aly, *et al.* [76] and Charabi, Rhouma, and Gastli [77]. For wind turbines, by Baban and Parry [78] and Abdul Baseer and Alhems [79] and a wind feasibility study for Massachusetts by Carlino [80] also used a maximum slope. Laos is highly mountainous and an exclusion of land based on a slope threshold is required to produce realistic results. Both additions can be used generically for studies in other countries and are beneficial to implement in GeoH2 to produce more realistic results.

3.1.1 Optimising Buffer Size for Complete Hexagon Coverage

The placement of hexagons is done with the SPIDER repository by using the `h3pandas` Python package, which is based on the `H3` hexagons. This requires an AOI and distributes hexagons throughout that area. However, there remained gaps at the border. This is solved by increasing a buffer zone until the AOI is fully covered.

3.1.1.1 Coordinate Reference System Transformation The input area is defined within the EPSG:4326 geographic coordinate system, characterised by coordinates in terms of longitude and latitude. To facilitate calculations in metres, which are relevant for the iterative increase of buffer width, a reprojection to the EPSG:4088 coordinate reference System (CRS) is carried out. The transformation from geographic coordinates (longitude, latitude) to projected coordinates (x, y) is expressed by the function

$$(x, y) = (f_x(\text{lon}, \text{lat}), f_y(\text{lon}, \text{lat})) \quad (1)$$

with f_x and f_y specify the reprojection to the EPSG:4088 CRS.

3.1.1.2 Buffering the Area of Interest The complete coverage by hexagons is achieved by expanding the AOI with a buffer. A distance d in metres is added to the boundary of the AOI, expressed as

$$(x', y') = (x + \Delta x, y + \Delta y) \quad (2)$$

with Δx and Δy being calculated with $\sqrt{(\Delta x)^2 + (\Delta y)^2} = d$. This can be easily done with the GeoPandas packages and the function `geopandas.GeoSeries.buffer()`.

3.1.1.3 Hexagon Grid Generation After buffering, the AOI is reprojected to the EPSG:4326 to create hexagons using the H3 spatial indexing. The H3 system generates hexagons by mapping geographic coordinates (longitude, latitude) to hexagon indexes at a specified resolution. In this context, a resolution of 5 is used, corresponding to an average hexagonal area of 252.9 square kilometres [81].

3.1.1.4 Iterative Buffer Optimisation and Coverage Validation A while loop was deployed to iteratively increase the buffer size until the hexagons fully cover the AOI, which is checked with the function `check_coverage()`. The buffer size is incrementally expanded until the function yields a Boolean true, indicating full coverage. This condition is expressed as

$$\text{Coverage} = \forall p \in A, p \in H \quad (3)$$

where A is the geometry of the input area, H is the union of all hexagons, and p represents any point within A . The notation $\forall p \in A$ ensures that every point in the AOI is considered when checking against the union of hexagons H_u . This is done by $p \in H$ checking if a point p from A is within H_u , confirming that the union of hexagons covers every point. This procedure is carried out in EPSG:4088 CRS using the Geopandas function `covers()`, which verifies the full coverage of each aligned geometry by returning a true value. Before this evaluation, individual hexagons are combined into one area H_u via the function `unary_union()`. The condition for complete coverage is met when all geometries yield a Boolean true. As a last step, the duplicates have to be dropped with `drop_duplicates(subset="h3_index")`. In this context, the optimal buffer size has been determined to be 11 kilometres, exceeding the 8.5-kilometer incircle radius of the specified hexagons. A total of 940 hexagons cover the area of Laos.

3.1.2 Slope-Based Exclusion for Solar and Wind Placement

The placement of wind turbines and photovoltaic panels is facilitated through GLAES, which systematically identifies regions suited for renewable energy generation. The main purpose of GLAES is to assess land eligibility, implementing area restriction to ensure that PV panels and wind turbines are placed exclusively on suitable terrain. In the original repository, GLAES is used

to exclude the following areas: Coastal areas, herbaceous wetland, built-up area, permanent water bodies. However, Laos is highly mountainous and it is essential to implement a restriction based on slope gradients to ensure the accuracy and feasibility of the resulting spatial assessments.

3.1.2.1 Preprocessing of the Digital Elevation Model A DEM, providing a rasterised representation of altitude, is used to calculate the slope. Pre-processing through smoothing of the DEM is crucial to diminish abrupt altitude fluctuations that otherwise compromise the outline of the excluded regions. Through that, the terrain features are enhanced and the slope calculations are more stable. Here, land availability analysis is used to employ a systematic methodology and identify topographic trends, rather than providing a granular representation.

Through the function `scipy.ndimage.gaussian_filter` a multidimensional Gaussian filter is applied, where the standard deviation σ filters along the x and y axes. This filter suppresses high frequency, which corresponds to rapid changes in altitude within our DEM [82]. It also minimises spatial spread, implying that the effect diminishes with increasing distance from the central point [82]. Through that, the filter has a very localised affect. The Gaussian function is defined by

$$G(x, y) = \frac{1}{2\pi\sigma^2} \exp\left(-\frac{x^2 + y^2}{2\sigma^2}\right) \quad (4)$$

where x and y are the coordinates relative to the center, and σ is the standard deviation parameter determining the level of smoothing [83]. This filter is applied by convolving the DEM raster with a Gaussian kernel, which is a matrix of values that has a bell-shaped profile in two dimensions. Here, a σ value of 2 is used. The effect of the Gaussian filter is visualised in Figure 11.

Figure 11: Application of the gaussian filter on a digital elevation model. Own illustration.

Gradients in the east (x) and north (y) directions are calculated with the Sobel operator. This is done for G_x and G_y with

$$G_x = \frac{\text{Sobel}(\text{DEM}), \text{axis} = 1)}{2 \times \text{pixel_size}_x} \quad (5)$$

$$G_y = \frac{\text{Sobel}(\text{DEM}), \text{axis} = 0)}{2 \times \text{pixel_size}_y} \quad (6)$$

with `pixel_size` being the approximate pixel size in metres. It was necessary to apply a latitude correction to account for the pixel size distortion caused by the Earth's curvature [84]. In Python this is done with Numpy `np.cos(np.radians(latitude))` where the cosine function scales the pixel size. The slope at each pixel is then calculated with

$$\text{Slope} = \arctan\left(\sqrt{G_x^2 + G_y^2}\right) \quad (7)$$

where the `arctan` converts the gradient into an angle [85].

3.1.2.2 Wind Energy Exclusion Function The evaluation of wind energy potential is conducted by applying a threshold condition to the computed slope matrix with

$$\text{Mask}_{wind} = (\text{Slope} \geq \text{Threshold}_{wind}) \wedge \text{BinaryMask} \quad (8)$$

where the threshold defines which slope to exclude. In Abdul Baseer and Alhems [79] multiple studies are compared, which considered a maximum range for slopes between 10-30% (around 5-17 degrees). Baban and Parry [78] considered a maximum slope of 10 % while Abdul Baseer and Alhems [79] considered 15% the upper limit as feasible for wind turbines. In Carlino [80] the upper limit was even 16.5 degrees. Here, a slope of 15% equal to 8.53 degrees is taken as the maximum slope, which excludes 78.02% of the AOI.

The predominant wind direction in Laos from 2016 to 2024 is east [86]. This is observed for an average duration of seven months, extending from September to April, during which the wind velocity during the period is higher than the annual average [86]. Consequently, wind turbines are orientated to maximise power output towards this orientation, following the guideline established by Patel's rule of thumb [87]. The optimal placement for wind turbines is a separation of around 10 rotor diameters in the optimal direction, and 4 rotor diameters in the perpendicular direction [87], [88]. Here, a Vestas V80 - 2 MW with a diameter of 80 m is selected [89]².

3.1.2.3 Solar Energy Exclusion Function In the context of solar energy, it is crucial to account for the orientation, referred to as the aspect. The aspect is calculated with

$$\text{Aspect} = \arctan 2(-G_y, G_x) \quad (9)$$

The varying effectiveness of PV installations is captured by associating a higher slope threshold to the south aspect, ranging from 135°-225°, which receives more solar insolation. For the north-east-west aspect, the range is 45°-135° and 225°-315°, a lower slope threshold is set. The exclusion mask for PV is defined as

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Mask}_{pv} = & [(Aspect \in [45^\circ, 135^\circ] \vee Aspect \in [225^\circ, 315^\circ]) \wedge \\ & (Slope \geq \text{Threshold}_{north_east_west})] \vee \\ & [(Aspect \in [135^\circ, 225^\circ]) \wedge (Slope \geq \text{Threshold}_{south})] \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

where the threshold is defined based on the north-east-west and southern aspects.

There is no universally recognised maximum slope beyond which PV panels cannot be effectively installed. In Elboshy, Alwetaishi, M. H. Aly, *et al.* [76], an upper limit of an 11% gradient, equal to 6.28 degrees, was deemed suitable; however, terrains exhibiting a gradient of less than

²The original repository contained an error in which the maximum capacity for each hexagonal cell was incorrectly specified per turbine rather than per megawatt (MW). In PyPSA, the maximum capacity within the investment model is in MW, and consequently the value was multiplied by the rated power of the selected turbine. The same error existed for PV placement

1% were identified as optimal. For south-facing photovoltaic panels, a higher inclination between 10 and 23 degrees is particularly suitable, according to the findings of Charabi, Rhouma, and Gastli [77]. However, inclined terrains are also effective, as the arrays can be more densely packed, thereby improving productivity per unit area [77], [90]. If the angle is higher than 16 °, the energy output per unit space by 48% [90]. This effect is valid and practical up to 33 degrees [77]. In this context, regions were methodically excluded for the north-east-west orientations with slopes exceeding 6.28 degrees, and for the south-facing aspect with slopes surpassing 33 degrees. This condition excludes 51.58% of the AOI.

Setting the spatial distribution of solar farms comes with challenges, as research dedicated to this particular issue is low. Although there exist methodologies for the placement of solar farms, often they do not account for the large scale of the model used in this study, nor do they assume the use of all identified areas [91]–[94]. The typical size of solar farms in the United Kingdom is around 5 MW [95]. According to Sukumaran, Sudhakar, Yusop, *et al.* [96], a 5 MW solar farm has an area of approximately 44,000 m^2 (10 acres). This differs from other sources, saying that around 101,000 m^2 (25 acres) are needed for 5 MW [97], [98]. According to *Everything You Need to Know About Solar Farm Requirements* [98], for 1 MW an area of 6-8 acres is needed in the UK. This differs from a study that calculates 6197.6 m^2 (1.5 acres) for 1 MW [99].

In the original repository, the MW per PV unit is not specified and the spatial requirements per unit of solar energy production vary significantly between the selected studies. Given the theoretical scope of this analysis, the estimations derived from the PV modelling performed by Umar, Bora, Banerjee, *et al.* [99] will be used here. The area of 6197.6 m^2 corresponds approximately to a square with a side length of 79 metres. A square is chosen because photovoltaic panels will not be arranged in a circular layout. Consequently, the PV placement dots need to be spaced by half of the diagonal to avoid overlap if the dot position is not completely straight but curved. Half of the diagonal is 56 m. It is clear that five 1 MW solar farms will not be built next to each other; they will be moved together. Hence, the spacing between the placement dots can be regarded as overly cautious³. Furthermore, it is possible that a node is on the edge of an excluded area, requiring its relocation. If two nodes are positioned at the periphery of an excluded region, it is plausible that they converge towards one another. This results in additional spacing requirements of two times the initial length, here 112 m. Collectively, this leads to a spacing of 224 m.

3.1.2.4 Application of Mask in subsequent Steps The present mask is implemented next with other exclusions within the GLAES framework. Based on the remaining areas after exclusion, the location of wind turbines and photovoltaic panels is performed. Although this exclusion may appear stringent, it represents a plausible scenario of land availability for renewable energy.

3.2 Feature Additions to GeoH2

Additions to power generation included the incorporation of hydropower and grid capacity, as illustrated in Figure 10. Although the incorporation of grid integration constitutes a valuable enhancement, it is based upon several assumptions and therefore will not be incorporated into the primary model.

³An improvement would be to consider the available area per Hexagon

3.2.1 Integration of Hydropower

The incorporation of hydropower is pivotal for the assessment of Laos, owing to its significant hydropower potential. Until now, GeoH2 has only integrated solar and wind energy. Complementing wind and solar energy, hydropower is an additional power source for hydrogen production. In the context of GeoH2, this integration is implemented through the repositories *GeoH2-data prep* and *GeoH2* repository. Figure 12 illustrates the procedure executed within the *GeoH2-data prep* repository beginning with the generation of a GeoPackage file and ending in a conversion to a hexagon file with the hydropower capacity.

Figure 12: Integration of hydropower in the repository GeoH2-data-prep

The *GeoH2-master* requires two inputs, as shown in Figure 13, each serving distinct functions. It is necessary to have specific hydroelectric data and locations to obtain unique runoff data for each site through the Atlite package. Hydro-specific data includes the commercial operating date (COD), hydraulic head, and domestic capacity. The second file consists of the aggregated hydro capacity per hexagon and the number of solar farms and wind turbines. In the following, both processes will be explained in more detail encompassing the stages from preprocessing, to intermediate calculations to the final geospatial mapping.

Figure 13: Integration of hydropower in the repository GeoH2

3.2.1.1 Preprocessing Hydro Data The dataset with the hydropower plant’s geographical coordinates is obtained from an Excel file that contains details of various hydroelectric

plants within Laos. The coordinates are in EPSG:4326 CRS format. This was transformed into a GeoPackage file to feed into the [SPIDER](#) repository, which generates a hexagonal layout throughout Laos. For hydropower, the capacity for each hexagon is aggregated using a sjoin operation, which is a spatial join between two GeoDataFrames. Both files are used as input for the *GeoH2* repository.

The hydropower dataset provided by the MEM includes information on location, capacity, expected output, COD, head, and fuel type. The fuel type splits hydropower into run-of-river and reservoir-type hydropower projects. A run-of-river project is typically a canal application without changing the original course of the river [100]. It requires only limited flooding and can be designed with a small head, but is highly dependent on river discharge [101]. In contrast, reservoir-type projects accumulate water through dam structures to allow for flow regulation [101]. Such projects consist of a reservoir with a dam and can have much greater impacts on the environment [100].

However, the data set is fragmented, and subsequent analysis revealed discrepancies between the provided head and the expected power output. As a result, parts of the head data were updated with values from HoboMaps [102], the remaining head values were calculated using a computational methodology.

3.2.1.2 Hydraulic Head Calculation The hydraulic head is determined by extracting a bounding box around each hydropower location and integrating this selected area with a DEM, along with data on river flow and flow accumulation. A visualisation and overview of the process is given in Figure 14. The first step involves the mentioned selection of an area around each hydropower site, which is followed by the calculation of the head and iterative optimisation of the buffer. Comparable methodologies were used in related studies, mainly to evaluate the overall potential or to identify prospective sites [103], [104]. However, the objective in this study is to

Figure 14: Hydraulic head calculation based on a DEM

estimate the hydraulic head of existing sites, which has not been implemented in this specific manner. Isolating a bounding box is crucial for this objective, since the location of the site is known.

The bounding box around each hydropower site is adjusted through a buffer b , that expands

the square in each direction from the central coordinate:

$$\begin{aligned} \min x &= \text{Lon}_{\text{plant}} - b, & \min y &= \text{Lat}_{\text{plant}} - b, \\ \max x &= \text{Lon}_{\text{plant}} + b, & \max y &= \text{Lat}_{\text{plant}} + b \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

In this study, three different methods are compared, given the importance of the hydraulic head in the hydropower potential equation:

- A) Subtracting the elevation of the hydropower plant from the highest elevation within the buffer zone:

$$\text{Head} = \max(\text{DEM}) - \text{hydropower_elevation} \quad (12)$$

- B) Subtracting the elevation of the lowest from the highest elevations within the buffer area:

$$\text{Head} = \max(\text{DEM}) - \min(\text{DEM}) \quad (13)$$

- C) Creating a local hydrological network around each hydroelectric plant based on DEM and flow accumulation. The hydraulic head is determined by identifying the segment within the hydrological network that exhibits the highest elevation drop:

$$\text{Head} = \max(\text{head}_{\text{arc}}) \quad (14)$$

Methods A and B are based solely on the DEM, which is done with `NumPy` after the extraction of the area. The hydrological network involves the river flow and flow accumulation and creates a network of nodes and arcs, making it more complex. Method C will be explained in more detail.

Within the extracted area, a grid of nodes is created for each cell with four attributes: coordinates, elevation, flow path, and flow accumulation. A node $N(i, j)$ is defined by the row i and column j , which can be transformed by a matrix transformation into coordinates. By storing this information in the node, it effectively captures the elevation and flow accumulation for the following steps. The segment, or arc, represents the flow paths denoted by

$$\text{arc}(N(i, j) \rightarrow N(i', j')) \quad (15)$$

and connects two nodes, representing the flow paths. This dictates the path of the river through the terrain and consequently the hydraulic head.

The next node $N(i', j')$ is determined by following this flow using the D8 method, which maps the flow direction in eight possible directions [105]. This technique is very well suited for terrain analysis, in which the hydrological flow is influenced by the topography. Here, this is done with

$$(i', j') = \text{flow_direction_to_idx}(i, j, \text{direction}(i, j)) \quad (16)$$

where the direction is given by manipulating the row index i and column index j . Figure 15 illustrates the process by which the subsequent node is determined by altering the two indices. Although it may initially appear counterintuitive that the south direction is at the top, it is reasonable within the grid of nodes. An increment in the y-axis, here an increase in the row number, translates to progressing

Figure 15: Own illustration of the directions with the D8 Method.

downward in the table, and hence southward in geographical terms. Therefore, the orientation of the map is horizontally flipped within the node grid. The x-axis corresponds to the column index j , which remains consistent with the geographical orientation. If the flow direction leads to a valid neighbouring node, an arc is created between the two nodes with the start and end node.

The hydraulic head is then determined as the difference in elevation between the start node $N(i, j)$ and the end node $N(i', j')$. The maximum head is identified with the already defined equation 14, to find the most significant potential drop within the buffer. The algorithm systematically iterates through each arc, computing the elevation drop and comparing it to the current arc's value. The elevation drop within each arc is calculated with

$$\text{head_arc} = \text{elevation}(N(i, j)) - \text{elevation}(N(i', j')) \quad (17)$$

The location of the hydropower plants is often not located directly along the river flow, also visible in Figure 16. The bounding box gives the algorithm the flexibility to select the best match based on the surrounding area, and not on the plant location defined in the dataset. The figure also illustrates the arcs that represent the river flow within the selected area.

Figure 16: Own illustration of created hydronetwork.

3.2.1.3 Hydro-type specific Buffer Optimisation Optimising the buffer b is the subsequent step, upon which the best-fit method A, B, or C is selected. The buffer area is optimised by minimising the combined value of the mean absolute error (MAE) and the standard deviation (STD) from a range of buffer sizes. The MAE of the head difference between actual head and calculated head eliminates the direction of the error and reduces the magnitude of the error:

$$\text{MAE} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |\text{head}_i - \text{head_calculated}_i| \quad (18)$$

Method	Buffer size (m)		MAE (m)		STD (m)	
	Reservoir	Run-off-river	Reservoir	Run-off-river	Reservoir	Run-off-river
A	226	297	41.95	57.20	41.02	83.34
B	202	116	31.01	51.20	38.83	86.12
C	357	337	26.08	45.85	29.08	84.40

Table 3: Optimal buffer size, MAE, and STD for hydraulic head calculation for methods A, B, and C.

Adding the STD reduces variability, resulting in more reliable estimates:

$$\text{STD} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (\text{head_difference}_i - \overline{\text{head_difference}})^2} \quad (19)$$

The combined metric represents a balance between accuracy, by the MAE, and consistence, through the STD.

Run-of-river and reservoir-type projects impose distinct impacts on their respective environment, thereby influencing the head calculation. The hydraulic head for run-of-river projects is determined by the river flow. However, there exists the potential to construct a storage reservoir, which allows to stabilise the flow for power generation [101]. For reservoirs, the head is artificially increased by creating an upstream reservoir through the dam structure [100], [101]. Consequently, categorising the types of hydropower projects tailors the buffer to these characteristics.

As mentioned above, the optimal method was selected based on the lowest MAE and STD. The marginal difference between the equations of Methods A and B justifies an exploratory analysis. Figure 17 shows box plots of the mean error and MAE. The box denotes the interquartile range (IQR), ranging from the 25th to the 75th percentile, the middle line marking the median, and the red diamond the mean. The whiskers extend from the edges of the box to the minimum and maximum data points that lie within 1.5 times the IQR of the lower and upper quartiles, defined by the Python package `matplotlib.pyplot.boxplot` [106]. If there are points beyond this range, they are considered outliers, and the whisker goes to the maximum point within the range. Should the whiskers be shorter than the specified range, it implies a higher density of data points, potentially indicating a skewed distribution.

Examining Figure 17a, the close proximity between the mean and median values of Method A strongly suggests a normal distribution. The mean is above zero, so it underestimates the head on average. There are significant outliers in the runoff calculation. The box plot of Method B, Figure 17b, has similar tendencies with a skewed distribution to underestimated values. However, the head of reservoirs is more frequently overestimated. Analysing the absolute values presented in Figures 17c and 17d, it is evident that Method B has a lower MAE and higher density. Both methods have two outliers for run-off-river plants, potentially indicating anomalies within those specific plants.

The optimal buffer size, next to the MAE and STD, for the three methods is shown in Table 3. In summary, Method C produces better results than Methods A and B, indicated by its substantially lower MAE and lower STD. The buffer size for Method C is larger than the other two methods, which could be due to the river-guided network and consequently the lower elevation change.

Figure 17: Boplot diagrams of Method A and B showing mean error and mean absolute error.

Figure 18: Boplot diagrams of Method A,B and C showing the relative mean error.

Interesting is the comparison between reservoir and run-off-river plants. As mentioned above, a reservoir increases the hydraulic head artificially and in this data set has a higher average head than run-off-river plants. The average reservoir head is 68.5 metres and the average run-off-river head is 55.5 metres. For Methods A and B, this should result in a larger buffer size for reservoirs than run-off-river plants. Surprisingly, Method A exhibits a smaller reservoir buffer. This observation is due to the given location in the hydropower dataset, which is the location of the power station rather than the centre of the river. Consequently, Method A is inaccurate for this data.

In Figure 18, the relative mean error for each plant is visualised to demonstrate the extent of the inaccuracies. The underestimation of the head does not exceed 100%. The degree of overestimation varies between reservoir and run-off-river plants, with the former having lower inaccuracies, not beyond 150%. In contrast, run-of-the-river plants exhibit outliers reaching values up to 11 times the actual value. Analysing the relative distribution of the run-off-river, method B stands out with a notably dense distribution and low error margin. Values are predominantly underestimated, and the distribution is skewed to the left. This is further evident in the relative MAE, indicating for run-of-river plants a very close performance between Method B and Method C, with values of 141% and 143%. However, to be consistent with one method and due to better overall metrics, head calculations are based on Method C. Out of the total 123 hydropower plants, head values were missing for 72 and were calculated with Method C.

3.2.1.4 Hydropower Potential Calculation A visualisation of the hydropower potential process is given in Figure 13. The estimation of hydropower output P is based on

$$P = Q \times H \times \eta \times \rho \times g \quad (20)$$

with Q being the flow rate, H the head, η plant efficiency, ρ the density of water, and g the standard acceleration of gravity. The plant efficiency η is assumed to be 75%, consistent with the upper limit of plant efficiency observed in Nepal [107]. Within the *GeoH2-master* repository, the computation is done with the function `hydropower_potential()`, utilising the inputs η , Q , and H to obtain the hydropower capacity in MW.

The flow rate Q is calculated by

$$Q = R \times A \quad (21)$$

with the runoff R in m/s , and the catchment basin A in m^2 . The result is consequently in m^3/s . The flow rate Q is estimated with ATLITE and the function `cutout.hydro()`, which computes an inflow time series for the plant by aggregating over a given catchment basin. The basin is based on the hydrobasin model from Hydrosheds [107]. Atlite provides the output as an `xr.array` in m^3/h . Subsequently, this output is converted to m^3/s to compute the hydropower potential.

In the context of PyPSA optimisation, both the installed capacity and capacity factor are prerequisite parameters. The installed capacity is derived from the provided data set. The capacity factor is calculated by limiting the theoretical potential to the rated capacity C with

$$\text{Capacity Factor} = \frac{\min(P_{\text{MW}}, C)}{C} \quad (22)$$

This is done in the `hydropower_potential_with_capacity()` in combination with the function `xr.apply_ufunc` to compute the hydropower potential across all hydropower plants. In this function, the potential is calculated with the function `hydropower_potential()` and then the capacity factor is calculated with equation 22. Here, this is on an hourly basis for one year.

The calculated head values were compared with the expected generation (GWh) and the total possible generation (GWh) values that were given in the original data set, shown in Table 4. The

	# of hydropower plants	% of hydropower plants
Missing theoretical possible generation	14	19%
Within the range of expected and theoretical possible generation	47	65%
Outside the range of expected and theoretical possible generation (<10%)	9	13%
Significantly above or below given generation	2	3%

Table 4: Analysis of computed hydraulic head based on given expected and theoretical possible generation.

column "Expected Generation in (GWh)" had entries for all plants, while the column "Total Theoretical Possible Generation (GWH)" contained values. This process acted as verification to verify whether the calculated head values fell within the anticipated range. For this, the capacity factor was aggregated and then multiplied with the rated capacity. 14 of the 72 hydropower plants that did not have head values also did not have the corresponding theoretical generation values. The validation of these plants could not be carried out. However, most of them were within the range, which reinforces reasonable head values. Nine hydropower plants, representing 13% of the total, exhibited deviations of up to 10% from the expected range, while only two plants showed significant deviations beyond 50% this range. This underscores that the adopted methodology for calculating hydropower potential yielded plausible results.

3.2.1.5 Geospatial Mapping of Hydropower Plants to Hexagon The individual capacities and capacity factors of hydropower plants must be joined for each hexagon. This is done with a spatial join between the hydropower plant locations and the hexagon grid to associate each plant with the corresponding hexagon:

$$\text{Mapping} : H_i \rightarrow \text{Hexagon}_j, \quad \text{if Plant } H_i \text{ is within Hexagon } j \quad (23)$$

The `gpd.sjoin` function was used with the predicate set to `within`, ensuring that each plant was mapped to the hexagon that contains it. For hydropower capacities, this is a straightforward sum and was done in the *GeoH2-data-prep* repository. In contrast, capacity factors require a weighted average. The capacity factor for each hexagon CF_{hex} is calculated by

$$CF_{\text{hex}} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (CF_i \cdot W_i)}{\sum_{i=1}^n W_i} \quad (24)$$

with the capacity factor of each plant i , and its total capacity W_i as weight. This is performed iteratively until each hexagon has a hydro profile.

3.2.1.6 Application of Hydro Profile in subsequent Steps The hydro profile, comprising the capacity factors for each hexagon, is used in the PyPSA optimisation alongside the wind and solar profiles to meet the hydrogen demand. For that, the hydro profile and the maximum capacity in each hexagon is given as input to the function `optimize_hydrogen_plant()`.

3.2.2 Integration of Grid Electricity

The integration of grid electricity is based on the assumption that, at any given point along a transmission line, the transmission capacity is operating at its maximum threshold and available for use. This is a large assumption, and the feature requires much further development to provide an output. Nevertheless, it demonstrates how access to grid electricity can effectively mitigate the costs associated with the variability of renewable energy sources. Figure 19 illustrates this integration. The transmission grid data for Laos was sourced from [Open Infrastructure Map](#). This dataset was merged with the hexagon file, and the capacity of the highest value line was incorporated as a column; otherwise, a value of zero was assigned to the grid capacity. For PyPSa, a capacity factor represented by an xr.array profile filled with ones was used, assuming that the grid electricity is continuously available.

Figure 19: Integration of transmission capacity in GeoH2

3.3 Forecast of Urea Demand

Information on fertiliser consumption in Laos remains extremely sparse, with specific data on Laos' demand not being publicly accessible. For forecasting, quantitative data over longer periods is crucial, which has been provided so far exclusively by Our World in Data [70]. The use of fertilisers from 1988 to 2019 has been recorded with a demand of 63,799 tons in 2019 of synthetic fertilisers, which includes synthetic inputs of nitrogen, potassium, phosphorus and organic nitrogen. The Laotian Times [68] reported a fertiliser demand of 2 million tons annually, which includes synthetic and organic fertilisers and is consequently not usable here. Although other sources have studied the use of fertilisers in Laos, they generally abstain from estimating total demand.

Furthermore, research on urea forecasting remains limited. In the study presented by Kim and Brorsen [108], a method specifically designed for urea forecasting is described; however, its applicability is constrained here by the absence of data on corn prices, oil prices and annual gas prices for Laos. In particular, this study references only one additional method dating back to 1991, highlighting the minimal attention the subject has received. Kabir and Jalil [109] divides the forecast according to distinctive crops, yet this approach is also inapplicable in this

context. Danlami [110] provides a comprehensive review of the determinants that influence fertiliser demand in various studies, noting the persistent lack of consensus on contributing factors. Specific to Laos, Phongoudome [51] provides an overview of where the different crops were produced in 2010, but no indication of fertiliser usage. FAO [111], provides an extensive overview of fertiliser demand in Laos, explaining crop production and fertiliser use in Laos, but without including historical data.

Figure 20: Correlation between four values

A more granular data set was inaccessible for this analysis; hence, the data obtained from Our World in Data were utilised. In addition, indices of crop production, food production and the development of agricultural land specifically for Laos were used as determinants that influence the demand for urea [112]. A regression analysis with correlation values is shown in Figure 20, supporting its usage here. The Laotian government has established an objective to increase agricultural production by 2.5% annually, which was used to project future metrics for the agricultural food production index and the crop production index [113]. The last figure on the right depicts the relationship between fertilisers and GDP, which is also high. The GDP data from the World Bank [114] also provides a forecast until 2030, which is ideal for this forecast. As GDP represents part of the economy, fertiliser usage is either directly or through agricultural activity reflected [115].

Figure 21: Forecast of urea demand in Laos with linear regression from 2020 to 2029

In Figure 20 is also the correlation between fertiliser use and GDP shown, indicating a high correlation. The GDP data from the World Bank [114] includes projections extending to

2030, making it optimal for forecasting purposes. Given that GDP includes a component of the economy, fertiliser usage is reflected either directly or through agricultural activities [115]. Based on this, the fertiliser demand, here only urea, was forecasted with a linear regression. It was trained on the future values of the two indeces and the GDP (Table 8).

3.4 Data Collection

The data collection is closely following the provided process outlined by Halloran, Leonard, Salmon, *et al.* [39]. This includes the selection of shapefiles and geopackages:

- Global Oceans and Seas geopackage [116]
- Laos country boundary shapefile from [Natural Earth Data](#)
- Existing roads from [OpenStreetMap](#)
- The Copernicus land cover dataset [117]

The previously mentioned datasets serve as input for the repository *Geoh2-Data-Prep* and are instrumental for the operationalisation of SPIDER and GLAES. Initially, the GeoH2 outputs were denominated in EUR/kg; however, for the purposes of this analysis, they have been converted to \$/kg, as specified in the Appendix B. This is done on the basis of the average exchange rate from 2022 for EUR to USD. This was done for the conversion parameters in the Appendix B.3. For the technology parameters in Appendix B.5 all costs were updated with sources in USD. Here, the electricity generation parameter in USD/kW goes up to 2050, which is essential for scenario analysis. The relevant data are tailored to Laos as shown in Table 9.

Hydropower data was provided by the Laotian MEM and is not publicly available. In addition, access to the draft of the national hydrogen strategy was granted, giving further access to assumptions and hydrogen production targets.

3.5 Scenario Analysis

The baseline considers hydropower plants installed up to 2022 with capital expenditures (CAPEX) for wind, solar, battery energy storage systems (BESS) and electrolyzer specific for that year. The scenarios are split into two tiers, which are shown in figure 22.

Figure 22: Visualisation of the scenario analysis with two tiers.

3.5.0.1 Split in Available Total and Domestic Hydropower Capacity The first tier consists of a split between the total hydropower capacity and the actual domestic available capacity, as outlined in the chapter 2.3.2. This is a relevant differentiation to highlight the different capacity of hydropower plants, since most of them provide electricity directly to neighbouring countries and will not be available to the Laotian industry. Information on the availability of this capacity and the timeline of IPP contracts for the domestic sector is not included in the provided hydropower dataset. It is plausible that domestic capacity may exceed the figures used herein, as certain hydropower plants are scheduled to be reintegrated partly or fully into the Laotian grid. Furthermore, the column on domestic capacity is incomplete, and there are no values for hydropower beyond 2030 and cannot be analysed beyond that. Both cases are considered to give a realistic LCOH estimate and an estimate based on the fully available capacity.

This capacity is further reduced to account for domestic electricity consumption. The available capacity $C_{\text{available}}$ is

$$C_{\text{available}} = C_{\text{installed}} \times \left(1 - \frac{C_{\text{installed}}}{D_{\text{hourly}}}\right) \quad (25)$$

with the aggregated installed capacity $C_{\text{installed}}$ and the hourly demand D_{hourly} . The hourly demand is derived from the annual demand and then divided into hours. As illustrated in Table 1 in Chapter 2.3.2, a noticeable decline in the total capacity ratio is observed, which decreases from 89% in 2022 to 79% in 2040. Domestic capacity, in particular, is significantly lower due to the surge in electricity demand that exceeds the rate of newly installed hydropower. Nevertheless, this is supposedly mitigated by the reintegration of hydropower resources into the Laotian grid from IPPs. The domestic capacity ratio is expected to decrease from 73% in 2022 to 35% by 2040. These two capacities will be used for the scenarios in the second tier.

3.5.0.2 Split in Three Dimensions The second level segments the analysis into three distinct dimensions: temporal, spatial, and seasonal. The temporal scenarios examine the variations under conditions of additional hydropower capacity and reduced future costs for renewable energy infrastructure and hydrogen production. Especially wind, solar, BESS, and electrolyzer have significantly reduced cost over time. This analysis is done for the years 2022, 2025, 2030, and the post-2030 period, as beyond 2032 the potential hydropower sites lack specified COD. For the post-2030 scenario, the costs for the year 2040 are taken. However, the scenario is labelled post-2030 on the assumption that the commission of multiple identified hydropower projects will extend beyond 2040. Vientiane, the capital of Laos, is placed as the demand centre, consistent with previous studies using GeoH2 [39], [42]. However, this does not necessarily represent a primary urea demand region, given its predominantly residential characteristics. Given that spatial demand is evaluated within another dimension, this is noted as a limitation of this temporal dimension. Figure 23a illustrates the distribution of hydropower sites across specified temporal intervals. Most of these installations have already been built. However, by 2025 an additional 19 hydropower plants are expected to be operational. By 2030, a further 8 installations are expected, with an additional 13 projected for post-2030. Especially at the border of Laos new hydropower sites are built, changing the spatial hydropower landscape.

The spatial scenarios are divided into the northern, central, and southern regions. These regions are defined by the Laotian Ministry of Energy and Mines (MEM) and are visible in Figure 23b. The black dots represent the centroids of each region which are determined by computing the centroid of each province and subsequently calculating the centroid of the aggregated provinces. These dots act as the demand location in the model. The regional demand is based on calculations from chapter 3.3, and is divided by the relative share of agricultural rice and maize production in the provinces. FAO conducted a comprehensive assessment of crop production at the provincial

Figure 23: Split of hydropower in temporal scenarios and regional split in spatial scenarios

level during the period 2018-2022 [111]. The predominant agricultural commodities in Laos include rice and maize, for which urea is well suited as a fertiliser, which justifies such a split [118], [119]. Due to data availability issues, a further analysis was not feasible, and basic weighted metrics were employed to split the total demand between these three regions. The northern demand represents 18%, the central demand 24%, and the southern demand 59%.

Figure 24: Dry and wet season for 2019 and 2022 respectively.

The climate impact scenario does not use Atlite to estimate the hydropower potential and instead uses actual factors of the hydropower capacity provided by MEM. Here, the hydrologically dry year 2019, and the wet year 2022 are compared, visible in Figure 24. This provides a robust representation of the potential disparities in the electrical output of the hydropower. Climate change influences precipitation patterns, which poses significant risks to hydropower generation, as it could result in extended periods of decreased electricity production [65]. Here, the monthly capacity factors are uniformly distributed into hourly timesteps to align with the hourly capacity

factors for solar and wind energy. This approach is crucial in illuminating the distinctions not only between the dry season, encompassing the period from November to April, and the wet season, extending from May to October, but also year-to-year variations, which can exhibit significant discrepancies. The year 2022 included additional hydropower facilities that were absent in 2019. Nevertheless, these sites were excluded for the purposes of the comparative analysis. The seasonal differences in the average capacity factors were shown in Table 2. In this context, the elasticity will be computed to demonstrate the impact of variations in the capacity factor on the LCOH. The calculation is performed using the following expression:

$$\text{Elasticity} = \frac{\% \text{ change in capacity factor}}{\% \text{ change in cost}} \quad (26)$$

This shows the percentage change on the LCOH resulting by a 1% alteration of the capacity factor. If the elasticity is greater than 1 it is highly sensitive to changes.

Figure 25: Eligible areas for solar and wind energy.

3.5.0.3 Excluded Areas across Scenarios The excluded areas remain the same for all scenarios and are split for wind and solar energy, as visible in the Figure 25. These exclusions are notably conservative. Exclusions are based on coastal areas, herbaceous wetlands, built-up areas, permanent water bodies, agricultural lands, national biodiversity conservation areas, and forest protection areas. The latter three categories are particularly distinctive to Laos, as they are legally designated zones. The difference between solar and wind stems mainly from different excluded slopes as outlined in Chapter 3.1.2.

3.5.0.4 Comparative Cost Equations All scenarios are compared along the LCOH, and the total costs. The total costs C_{total} are calculated in GeoH2 with

$$C_{\text{total}} = C_{\text{prod}} + C_{\text{road}} + C_{\text{tran}} + C_{\text{water}} \quad (27)$$

with road construction costs C_{road} , transport and conversion costs C_{tran} , production costs C_{prod} , and water cost C_{water} . In GeoH2, the term "production cost" corresponds to LCOH and has six components: hydro, solar, wind, electrolyzer, battery, battery storage. Each cost component C_{comp} is calculated with

$$C_{\text{comp}} = \text{Cap}_{\text{comp}} \times K_{\text{comp}} \times \text{CRF}_{\text{comp}} \quad (28)$$

where Cap_{comp} represents the installed capacity of each component in MW, K_{comp} the capital cost of each component, and CRF_{comp} the capital recovery factor specific to each component. The capital recovery factor (CRF) is calculated with

$$\text{CRF}_{\text{com}} = \frac{(1 + I_{\text{com}})^{L_{\text{com}}} - 1}{I_{\text{com}} \times (1 + I_{\text{com}})^{L_{\text{com}}}} \quad (29)$$

with the component specific interest rate I_{com} , and the component specific lifetime L_{com} [42].

4 Results

The base scenario for 2022 is analysed comprehensively, while subsequent scenarios within one dimension highlight deviations from this base scenario. The figures of the temporal, spatial and seasonal scenarios without significant changes are in Appendix D, E, and F, respectively.

4.1 Temporal Scenarios

4.1.1 Base Case Scenario - 2022

The results of the lowest total cost, either by truck or pipeline, for the base case scenario in 2022 are shown in Figure 26. A dark green shade indicates low total cost, whereas a shade closer to white indicates higher total costs. The grey hexagons indicate that the optimisation could not meet the entered demand. Of the 940 hexagons, 228 did not have feasible solutions, which are often located at the edges of the AOI. This phenomenon can be attributed to overlap with neighbouring countries, resulting in substantial exclusion zones within these hexagons. The grey hexagons in the inner northern region stem from extensive national biodiversity conservation zones and forest protection areas. For 708 hexagons, the trucking alternative is cheaper, which is greater than 99% of the feasible hexagons.

Figure 26: Scenario 2022 lowest cost hexagon map

The lowest total cost in 2022 is 2.80 \$/kg, going up to 23.58 \$/kg. The dark green spots that meander in a line in the north are the seven Nam Ou Dams⁴. These dams have a huge capacity of 1,272 megawatts and produce on average 5,046 GWh annually [102]. Through that they are very distinctive. These seven hexagons are in this scenario solely based on hydropower,

⁴HoboMaps provides a detailed description of them: [Link](#)

with hydropower capacities between 50 and 58 MW for trucking and pipeline. Interestingly, the hydropower capacity and compressed hydrogen storage are reduced with proximity to the demand centre. The hydrogen storage reduces from slightly above 30 tons of hydrogen storage (1028 MWh) to zero in the pipeline scenario. The trucking scenario requires 3 tons of hydrogen storage on average for the Nam Ou Dams.

Following an analysis of the spatial distribution between trucking and pipeline, a very similar behaviour can be deduced, with the pipeline mode demonstrating a marginally higher cost for the southern regions. This is visible in Figure 27, where the colour scale is limited to 18 \$/kg, to make this effect stronger. It is evident that, across the two transport modes, the utilisation

(a) Trucking total cost hexagon map

(b) Pipeline total cost hexagon map

Figure 27: Scenario 2022 (a) trucking and (b) pipeline total cost hexagon maps

of hydropower results in the lowest cost. For a deeper understanding, the different generation components were analysed independently and the hexagons were split into three categories:

- Hydro Hexagons: Select all rows where the hydropower capacity is greater than zero.
- Solar Hexagons: Select all rows where the solar capacity is greater than zero and both the hydropower and wind capacity are zero.
- Wind Hexagons: Select all rows where the wind capacity is greater than zero and the hydropower capacity is zero.

The exclusion of wind power from the analysis of hexagons with solar power is made because of the very low application of wind power. This is based on installed capacities, as shown below.

Hydropower is scattered in Laos with predetermined regions, visible in Figure 28a. The installed hydro power capacity is largely homogeneous, apart from the anomaly of the yellow hexagon. This anomaly arises from the restricted eligibility area within that hexagon. Here, solar power has a maximum installable capacity of 83 MW, which is reached, and is coupled with 34 MW of BESS. The installed hydropower capacity is more than 300 MW.

(a) Installed hydropower capacity

(b) Installed solar capacity

Figure 28: Scenario 2022 installed capacity of (a) hydropower and (b) solar energy per hexagon

Given that solar power exhibits the lowest capital expenditure (CAPEX), shown in Table 27, optimisation inherently favours its implementation. It is implemented in almost every hexagon with high capacity in the south, visible in Figure 28b. This aligns with the Global Solar Atlas, where solar irradiation is highest in the south [120]. The opposite behaviour is visible in Figure 29. Wind installations are limited to 13 hexagons, with a notable cluster in the South-East, which can be attributed to high wind speeds in that region, as evidenced by the Global Wind Atlas [5]. An anomaly exists with the yellow hexagon, which includes a wind capacity of 145 MW, the maximum available solar capacity at 283 MW, and additional 62 MW of battery storage. It also requires almost 800 tons of hydrogen storage. It can be deduced that there is a potential misalignment between the capacity factors of wind and solar installations and that both solar irradiance and wind velocity are suboptimal. The installed wind capacity generally remains below 40 MW.

Figure 29: Scenario 2022 installed wind capacity per hexagon

The total cost analysis in the three categories, as defined above, is shown in Figure 30. The behaviour of the installed capacities is also reflected in the costs. Hydropower has on average

Figure 30: 2022 Scenario Boxplot of average total costs splitted by pipeline and trucking across different hexagon categories: (1) with hydropower above zero, (2) with solar above zero and without hydro and wind, (3) with wind and without hydro and solar.

the lowest total costs, followed by solar and wind. The differences between pipeline and trucking are only incremental, with trucking slightly lower across all categories.

Notable is the low density of hydropower with total costs ranging from 2.3 to 18 \$/kg. This could be due to the characteristic of hydropower in this model. Given its more stable capacity factor compared to wind and solar, hydropower is consistently installed. When only a low capacity is available, the cost tends to follow the behaviour of typical solar and wind hexagons, resulting in higher \$/kg.

It is predictable that the least expensive 100 hexagons, determined by the LCOH, follow this cost profile. Hydropower hexagons are the cheapest, followed by solar hexagons in areas with high solar irradiation, requiring less capacity to be installed. This is visible in Figure 31, where especially the selected areas in the west indicate high solar irradiation toward these areas. Hydropower hexagons show the lowest costs, followed by solar hexagons situated in regions with substantial solar irradiation, which requires reduced installed capacity. This trend is illustrated in Figure 31, which highlights the selected western areas of Laos that have high irradiation levels, as mentioned before.

Figure 31: Visualisation of top 100 hexagons based on lowest LCOH values.

Although 99% of the hexagons have a lower total cost for trucking than pipeline hexagons,

Figure 32: 2022 minimal LCOH hexagon split by cost portions

the cheapest LCOH hexagon has transportation via pipeline. It is located at Nam Ou Dam 1 in the center north of Laos (Figure 52). Looking at the six cost components in Figure 32, shows that it is solely using hydropower. Hydropower makes 77% of the total LCOH, the remaining are from the electrolyzer. An explanation why it is cheaper than trucking is the more stable production due to constant transportation via pipeline. While the production has to be adapted to trucking to minimise the number of used trucks.

Figure 33: 2022 minimal LCOH hexagon compared to the average and median hexagon cost portions

Compared to the average and median hexagon, visible in Figure 33, this substantiates the previous analysis, indicating that the majority of the cells employ solar power with very low to no wind power. Notably, the adoption of batteries is relatively low, whereas the implementation of hydrogen storage systems is more prevalent. A factor could be the higher cost per MWh of BESS compared to compressed hydrogen storage. Another factor is that there is currently no capacity constraint for the electrolyzer within GeoH2, and with only solar installed it is natural to assume the electrolyzer capacity factor is certainly below 50%. Looking at the hydrogen storage

reveals a similar pattern, as the capacity grows similarly as electrolyzer, even though slightly less. Hydrogen storage demonstrates a comparable trend, with capacity expansion similar to electrolyzers. On average, it is installed in the model with a capacity of 3735 MW, corresponding to 112 tons of hydrogen. Typically, compressed hydrogen storage operates at pressures ranging from 200 to 300 bars, and such large capacities are atypical [121].

4.1.2 Comparative Analysis across Time Dimension

The minimum LCOH and total cost from scenario 2022 to post-2030 are shown in Figure 34. In the post-2030 scenario, with costs for 2040, the lowest LCOH is 2.10 \$/kg for pipeline, and 2.17 \$/kg for truck (Table 80). The cost hierarchy, with LCOH for pipeline transport being the most economical and the total cost favouring trucking, remains consistently intact. As explained above, for LCOH this has presumably to do with the absence of interruptions coming from transport by pipeline.

Figure 34: Minimum cost development across temporal dimension

In all scenarios, the hexagon with minimal cost has solely hydropower (Appendix D). The cost of hydropower per kW is presumed to remain constant. Consequently, the cost reduction can be attributed primarily to the decrease in electrolyzer CAPEX, which decrease from 600 \$/kW in 2022 to 450 \$/kW by 2030, and further drop to a range of 320-400 \$/kW in the period post-2030 (Table 25).

A spatial analysis of the results indicates a high degree of similarity, visible in Appendix D. The overall spatial distribution of costs remains predominantly characterised by minimal hydrogen costs associated with hydropower sites. Figure 35 shows the minimum total cost location across the temporal scenarios. For both trucking and pipeline, the location remains constant from 2022-2030. However, this paradigm shifts post-2030 with the commissioning of a new hydropower facility, the Sanakham Dam, which is projected to generate 369 GWh and has a capacity of 650 MW⁵. Most of this goes to Thailand, with only 10 MW reserved for the domestic electricity grid. Given this premise and considering the modelled hydropower capacity of 57 MW, this is not feasible within the constraints of the current IPP agreement.

Analogous to the similar distribution of costs is the pattern of hexagons lacking a feasible solution, as depicted in Figure 36. The modest increase from 228 hexagons in 2022 to 237 in the post-2030 scenario can be primarily attributed to a reduction in available hydropower generation coupled with an increased demand for hydrogen.

⁵Hobomaps provides more information: [Link](#)

Figure 35: Temporal scenarios - visualisaion of minimum hexagon based on total cost.

In future scenarios, hydropower generation diminishes due to a decrease in the total capacity ratio, which is inversely related to the projected rise in domestic electricity consumption. This is also the reason why the post-2030 scenario experiences massive outliers with a total cost greater than 80 \$/kg (Table 79).

Examining the average cost reveals a more pronounced decrease, approximately 30% between transport, trucking and pipeline, and cost options, LCOH and total cost. For the total cost of trucking and pipeline from 11.61 and 12.47 in 2022 to 9.12 and 9.88 \$/kg in the post-2030 scenario, visible in Figure 37. This is mainly attributed to the CAPEX of PV, which is projected to decrease from 1018 \$/kW to 629 \$/kW by 2040; a 38% drop. The average component costs of solar sink from 5.08 and 5.10 in 2022 to 3.6 and 3.63 in post-2030, for pipeline and trucking, respectively. This is a decrease of 30%, which is identical to the decrease of the cost component electrolyzer. Although the cost of compressed hydrogen storage was kept constant, the average cost decreased by 10%, showing on average a reduced need. Wind has a small to no effect on the average costs. With an average LCOH projected to remain at 8.8 \$/kg even post-

Figure 36: Temporal scenarios non-feasible hexagons

Figure 37: Average cost development across temporal dimension

2030 suggests that the majority of the hexagons is not cost competitive within an international market, where the current green hydrogen LCOH spans from 4-12 \$/kg [122].

Subsequently, the distribution of hexagons and total costs of hydrogen is analysed, depicted in Figure 38. Here, the results are visualised with a violin plot, which uses a density curve to depict the distribution. On the left are the individual points shown. Analysing the mean alone proves insufficient; thus, a violin chart was constructed to clarify the distribution over the temporal dimension. It is apparent that in the years 2022 and 2025, the distribution of hexagons demonstrates a higher density around the mean value, whereas for the years 2030 and beyond, the distribution becomes sparser. Despite the evident downward trajectory, it is also noteworthy that a nearly continuous line appears near the lower bound in all scenarios. These are attributed to hydropower plants that exhibit prolonged periods of a 100% capacity factor, likely a product of Atlite, but such extended durations are not typically observed in practice.

Figure 38: Violin chart of the lowest total cost across temporal dimension

Given that the majority of hexagons are not attractive for hydrogen production, an additional constraint is necessary. A selection of the 300 hexagons showing the lowest total cost was made across all temporal scenarios. It is visible for trucking in Figure 39, and for pipeline in Figure 40, that there is a clear movement of hexagons toward the south. The disparity is more noticeable in trucking scenarios, as minimisation of pipeline costs inherently favours proximate locations to the demand centre; here, Vientiane. This phenomenon can be attributed to the increase in solar irradiation in the southern regions and the concurrent decrease in PVCAPEX. As a result, the total cost within the top 300 hexagons remains comparatively high.

Figure 39: Temporal pipeline scenarios - Spatial distribution of the top 300 total cost hexagons.

Figure 40: Temporal trucking scenarios - Spatial distribution of the top 300 total cost hexagons.

The range of total cost within the top 300 hexagons is displayed in Table 5. In 2030, the top 300 hexagons fall below 10 \$/kg and remain also in the post-2030 scenario in the range of 2.50 \$/kg and above 8 \$/kg. This extensive range may result in the upper threshold lacking competitiveness in the international market [122]. Insightful is also the total hydropower capacity in hexagons with an LCOH below 3\$/kg. This reveals a significant potential, grounded in total hydropower capacities of 1,862 MW for 2022, 1,929 MW in 2025, 3,582 MW by 2030, and ultimately 5,977 MW post-2030.

Year	Min Pipeline	Max Pipeline	Min Trucking	Max Trucking
2022	3.15 \$/kg	12.35 \$/kg	2.80 \$/kg	12.19 \$/kg
2025	3.14 \$/kg	11.56 \$/kg	2.80 \$/kg	11.39 \$/kg
2030	2.97 \$/kg	9.74 \$/kg	2.65 \$/kg	9.54 \$/kg
Post-2030	2.72 \$/kg	8.70 \$/kg	2.50 \$/kg	8.53 \$/kg

Table 5: Range of Top 300 Hexagons by Vientiane pipeline and trucking total cost

4.2 Spatial Demand Scenarios

The minimal LCOH is 2.10 \$/kg for the northern, 2.31 \$/kg for the central and southern region, as shown in Table 30. The total cost is slightly higher at 2.70 \$/kg for northern, 2.89 \$/kg for central, and 2.83 \$/kg for the southern region. Nonetheless, the variations between regions are marginal, with discrepancies remaining below 10%. These disparities are further illustrated in Figure 83 and it is evident that the northern region exhibits the lowest cost, whereas the southern region experiences the highest. This phenomenon can be explained by the varying demand between regions, with the southern region exhibiting the highest demand. The total cost and LCOH indicate a marginally lower cost compared to the baseline scenario in Chapter 4.1.1, which assumed a higher demand. The minimal hexagons are powered exclusively by hydropower, with the remaining costs attributed solely to the electrolyzer CAPEX (Figure 84). This is consistent with the previous scenarios. Interestingly, the use of pipelines presents a more cost-effective solution to meet demand in the northern region, while the most economical approach for the central and southern regions involves trucking.

Examining Figure 41, which illustrate the minimum hexagon for each region, explains this phenomenon. The minimal hexagon in the northern region is positioned in close proximity to the demand centre, thus having minimal construction costs relative to those in the central and southern regions. In particular, in the southern region, the optimal hexagon is situated at a considerably greater distance.

Figure 41: Minimal hexagons by region

Figure 42: Violin chart of the pipeline and trucking total cost across spatial dimension

The selected minimal hexagons are analogous for both pipeline and transport, although their distribution patterns exhibit differences, as shown in Figure 42. For trucking the total cost have a much higher density than for pipeline, which has almost linear increasing transportation cost for longer distances. The distribution on the pipeline side partially reflects the distances from each hexagon to the demand center, because of the CAPEX calculation of pipelines. While, on average, trucking proves to be more cost-effective, this observation does not hold for the northern

Figure 43: Spatial pipeline scenarios - Distribution of the top 300 total cost hexagons.

Figure 44: Spatial trucking scenarios - Distribution of the top 300 total cost hexagons.

region, as previously mentioned.

Proceeding with the spatial analysis of the top 300 hexagons reveals a strikingly behavior for pipelines, a phenomenon that is similarly observable, though less pronounced, for trucking. The figures in 43 demonstrate that varying demand locations significantly influence the cost-efficiency of the top 300 hexagons. Notably, with the exception of select hexagons with available hydropower, the most economical hexagons differ substantially across each region within the top 300. The hexagons closest to the demand center are also the cheapest. This contrasts with the transportation via trucking, visible in the figure 44, where certain regions, particularly in the western outskirts, persist within the top 300. The southern scenario shown in Figure 44c exhibits a higher concentration of hexagons compared to the northern and central scenarios, a phenomenon likely attributable to the demand being twice as high in the southern region.

Figure 45 shows the average LCOH and the total cost of pipeline and trucking. The northern region has the lowest average total cost with 8.34 \$/kg, while it is considerably higher for central and southern around 11.5 \$/kg (Table 30). In the northern region, the average total cost associated with pipelines is over 70% higher. This discrepancy reduces to 30% in the central

Figure 45: Average total cost across spatial dimension

region and falls below 20% in the southern region. Conversely, LCOH in these regions increases by more than 3 \$/kg, which can be attributed to a higher demand. A good visualisation of this is shown in Figure 46, where the different cost components defined in Equation 28 are shown. The cost of solar and electrolyzer increases from northern to central and southern by 50%, which explains the price jump shown in Figure 45. The hydrogen storage remains constant, and the electrolyzer increases proportionally.

Figure 46: Average cost components across spatial dimension

4.3 Climate Impacts on Hydropower

In Figure 47, the minimum LCOH value is visible for 2019 with 7.77 \$/kg, and 2.67 \$/kg in the year 2022. The total cost is cheaper for trucking in both cases, with 8.21 \$/kg in 2019, and 3.29 \$/kg in 2022. The discrepancy between the two years is strikingly distinct, yet this is not represented in the average LCOH or the total cost. The mean values for both LCOH and the total cost remain essentially unchanged over the two years, as defined in Table 32. The average LCOH for 2019 and 2022 is approximately 11.35 \$/kg for pipeline, and 11.42 \$/kg for trucking. Examining the violin plot in Figure 89, which shows the total cost of hydropower

Figure 47: Climate Impact bar chart showing LCOH and total cost for 2019 and 2022

hexagons, reveals that the minimum cost for 2022 is an outlier and that the majority revolves around a similar average. The disparity in the average total costs of hydropower hexagons, as defined before, transported via pipeline between 2019 and 2022 is below 1%, while for trucking it slightly exceeds 1%. Notably, despite the substantial divergence in the capacity factor, the cost variation remains relatively minimal. This is also spatially reflected where hexagons with solely hydropower installed do not exist. Often it is a mixture of solar and BESS. The Nam Ou dams, clearly identifiable within the temporal and spatial scenarios, exhibit here, due to relatively low capacity factors, an average LCOH of 9.35 \$/kg for 2022 (Figure 88). This is only marginally lower than the average here. In contrast, within the 2019 scenario, only three such instances are visually noticeable in the hexagon map.

Figure 48: Comparison of hourly average capacity factor of 2019 and 2022 versus Atlite

This is related to the capacity factor. As evidenced in Figure 48, the capacity factors for the years 2019 and 2022 are observed to fall within a similar range, while the capacity factor

calculated using Atlite persistently predicts a higher availability of hydropower. This explains the significant disparity between the Climate Impact Scenario and the temporal and spatial dimensions. Nonetheless, the rationale behind the substantial overestimation of the capacity factor with the usage of Atlite is unclear. Furthermore, an examination of the capacity factors of the hydropower plants reveals that nine out of the 56 facilities assessed under the climate impact scenarios exhibited zero production for a duration of at least three months at the beginning of 2019. These plants include Nam Ngum Kengkuan, Nam Ngipe 2B, Nam Che 1, Nam Kap, Nam Pha Gnai, Nam Aow, Xekamarn 3, and Don Sahong.

The Don Sahong dam⁶ is in the far south and demonstrated exceptionally high and consistent production levels in 2022, resulting in the minimum hexagon cost of 2022 at 2.67 \$/kg. The identical hexagon exhibited zero installed hydropower capacity in 2019, instead relying on a combination of solar energy, BESS, and hydrogen storage. The Don Sahong dam only generates electricity for the domestic market and does not export its output. Consequently, a comprehensive comparative analysis was conducted between the minimal hexagon observed in 2019 and the Don Sahong Dam as recorded in 2022.

Looking at the cost components in 2019 for the minimum hexagon reveals that 54.2% are going to solar, 19.3% to electrolyzer, 17.5% to hydropower, and 8.9% to hydrogen storage (Figure 91). Wind or BESS is not installed. The cost increase in 2019 comes mainly from solar power, which is not existant in 2022. The share for 2022 is 79.8% for hydropower and the remaining to the electrolyzer (Figure 93). The hexagon in 2022 is solely fuelled by hydropower due to the stable capacity factor (Table 35). The change of each cost component between 2019 and 2022 is shown in Figure 95.

Figure 49: Change of cost components between 2019 and 2022 pipeline scenario

An analysis of the cost components in 2019 for the minimum hexagon reveals that 54.2% is assigned to solar, 19.3% to electrolyzer, 17.5% to hydropower and 8.9% to hydrogen storage (Figure 91). Neither wind nor BESS is installed. The higher costs observed in 2019 are primarily attributed to solar power, which is absent from the minimum hexagon in 2022. That share is primarily 79.8% for hydropower with the residual allocated to the electrolyzer (Figure 93). The hexagon in 2022 is exclusively powered by hydropower, attributed to its stable capacity factor (Table 35). The variations in each cost component between 2019 and 2022 are illustrated

⁶Hobomaps provide more information: [Link](#)

in Figure 49. As solar power is not used, its associated cost decreases to zero, resulting in a reduction of 4.21 \$/kg. The expenditures related to the electrolyzer and hydrogen storage decrease by 0.96 and 0.69 \$/kg, respectively. In contrast, the cost associated with hydropower increases by 0.77 \$/kg, culminating in a total LCOH of 2.67 \$/kg.

	LCOH Elasticity	Total Cost Elasticity
Pipeline	-1.7828	-1.1642
Trucking	-1.7598	-1.6258

Table 6: Elasticity of LCOH and total costs for climate impact scenario 2019 and 2022

The elasticity reveals an inverse correlation. Specifically, the elasticity of LCOH for the pipeline, measured at -1.78, implies that an increase in 1% in the hydropower capacity factor results in a 1.76% reduction in production cost. This is closely aligned with the elasticity of the LCOH of the trucking of -1.76. In particular, the elasticity of the total cost is comparatively lower, as the expenses associated with transport and conversion are not affected by variations in the capacity factor. This relationship is also visible in Figure 95.

5 Discussion

The minimum results for 2022 are presented in Table 7, clearly demonstrating that the northern spatial scenario produced the lowest LCOH and overall cost values. This is subsequently followed by the temporal base scenario and then the climate impact scenario for 2022. Consequently, it can be inferred that Laos, at the lower threshold, has the potential to produce hydrogen at a cost ranging from 2.1 to 2.67 \$/kg. In all scenarios, hydrogen was transported in the form of ammonia, and in the majority of cases, transportation via trucking emerged as the more cost-effective option. However, for hydrogen amounts of 7,400 tons, the optimal solution remains road transportation, but this could change for higher amounts when pipelines become economical.

	Min LCOH (\$/kg)	Min Total Cost (\$/kg)
Temporal Scenario 2022	2.31	2.80
Spatial Scenario Northern	2.10	2.70
Climate Impact Scenario 2022	2.67	3.29

Table 7: Minimum LCOH and total costs across different scenarios

Comparing these results with the other GeoH₂ outputs reveals a lower price than observed there. For Müller, Leonard, Trotter, *et al.* [42], the minimum LCOH identified in Kenya was 3.7 EUR/kg (around 4 \$/kg), and for Halloran, Leonard, Salmon, *et al.* [39] analysing Namibia it was 5.43 EUR/kg (around 6\$/kg). These differences are due to the integration of hydropower, which resulted in much lower values because of its low fluctuation. Looking at other studies, gives average of 2.3 EUR/kg (around 2.5 \$/kg) in 2030, which is consistent with this study since the hydropower CAPEX remains constant [123]. A more recent study in 2023 has a more conservative outlook, with 2.3 EUR/kg being achieved in 2050 [18]. However, looking at the DEEP Strategy, which outlines the Hydrogen Strategy for Laos and projects around 1.5 \$/kg by 2030, indicates that the computed values in this study are more consistent with the literature mentioned here.

5.1 Attractiveness of Solar, Wind, and Hydro Power

From the results across dimensions, it becomes clear that not all hexagons are particularly attractive for hydrogen production. This can be attributed to the performance of the analysed generators. Firstly, wind power installations are rarely observed within the model and, except for the region in the lower south of Laos, does not exhibit cost-effectiveness comparable to solar power; visible in Figure 29. Even with decreased costs towards 2040 this does not change, and it can be concluded, wind energy is within this model not attractive. Notably, the region exhibiting a high concentration of wind turbines within the model aligns with the location of a 600 MW wind farm under construction [124].

Secondly, solar power is the most installed generator. This can be primarily attributed to its lower assumed CAPEX, coupled with its extensive availability, as solar panels can be installed on 31% of Laos; double the amount of wind energy. In the context of Laos, solar energy represents the most accessible renewable energy source. According to the current Laos power development plan, solar capacity is projected to increase by 15.6 GW. However, this does not imply that it yields low LCOH values. Looking at the post-2030 scenario shows average values of 8 \$/kg for solar hexagons, which is not competitive on international markets for that period. A study estimated a minimum price of 1.4 \$/kg in 2030, less than a fifth of the value calculated in this study [123]. This disparity can be attributed to the low load factor of the electrolyzer, as BESS

is rarely used. Installing solely solar power and balancing with a large capacity of hydrogen storage is a major inaccuracy.

Third, hexagons with available hydropower consistently emerge as the most economical in all scenarios, because of their stable electricity generation. This is a key advantage for Laos and underscores why hydrogen production is a viable industry in the region. The violin graph within the temporal scenarios 38 revealed a consistent presence of hexagons with installed hydropower, having total costs below 3 \$/kg. With increasing installed hydropower plants in future scenarios, the number of hexagons falling below 3 \$/kg increases accordingly, consequently increasing the total hydropower capacity within these hexagons. This capacity is projected to increase substantially from 1,862 MW in 2022 to 5,977 MW in the post-2030 scenario, as mentioned before. Based on this, an estimate of the feasible hydrogen production capacity, with LCOH below 3 \$/kg, can be derived. Taking the assumption that 10 MW produces 181.3 kg of hydrogen per hour, as mentioned in María, Wang, Roy, *et al.* [125], this results in 1588 tons per year. This is almost identical to the H-TEC PEM Electrolyzer ME450 [126] with 187.5 kg of hydrogen per hour and 1,641 tons of hydrogen per year. Here, a range of annual production between 1,588 and 1,641 tons is assumed for a 10 MW electrolyzer. With almost 2 GW of hydropower in 2022 around 300,000 to 330,000 tons of hydrogen annually could be produced below 3 \$/kg. In the post-2030 scenario with 6 GW hydropower capacity, this amount would rise to the range of 950,000 and 980,000 tons of hydrogen. This is done under the assumption of continuous operation at full capacity, that the total available hydropower capacity is used for hydrogen production, and it has a capacity factor of 100%. The realistic estimate is expected to be lower, linked to domestic consumption and IPP contracts. Given the sensitivity of the model to the inputted demand parameters, it is plausible to assume a higher LCOH value if a higher demand is given.

5.2 Perspectives from the Temporal, Spatial, and Climate Impact Dimension

The analysed scenarios yielded distinctive insights. In terms of the temporal dimension, it is evident that with the future decrease in CAPEX renewables, the south-west region becomes increasingly attractive. This attractiveness is primarily driven by solar power, because most hydropower plants post-2030 are built in the north. However, the average LCOH marginally falls below 8\$/kg post-2030 which is still considered high. The most economically viable hexagons are always associated with hydropower without following a spatially driven trend. The hexagons exhibiting the lowest LCOH values remain nearly invariant, due to the consistent hydropower CAPEX. The observed cost reductions are mainly driven by the decrease in the electrolyzer CAPEX, which leads to a 9% reduced LCOH. It can be concluded that investment in hydrogen production is already profitable today, given the marginal observed cost reductions. Compared to future inflation, these cost reductions could potentially balance out against inflation.

Spatial analysis showed that the location of the hydropower plant is of some relevance if the objective is to meet the domestic demand for fertiliser. As expected, transportation via pipeline is highly cost-responsive to the production location, in contrast to the relatively invariant sensitivity observed for trucking. The southern region, which exhibits the highest demand, shows the highest sensitivity. Fulfilling domestic demand should consequently be optimised under a geospatial demand perspective. This requires a deeper understanding of the location of crops that predominantly use urea.

The Climate Impact scenarios revealed a disparity between the evaluated years 2019 and 2022, as well as between the two other dimensions. Although only two years were observed, constraining the broader applicability of the findings, it was shown that the effects of a dry and wet year can have an overproportionate effect on LCOH. If the capacity factor varies by

1%, this changes the LCOH by 1.75 - 1.80%. In this scenario, the transition from electricity generation with only hydropower to a mix comprising solar energy and hydropower, with solar energy predominating in electricity generation, explains this change. The differences from the other dimensions are based on the different assumed capacity factors for hydropower, as shown in Figure 48. Atlite assumed on average a much higher capacity factor, resulting in a lower cost.

5.3 Novelty and Contributions

This research is the first to analyse least-cost hydrogen production sites in Laos. This is partly attributable to the previously little data, as well as to the recent advances and increased interest in hydrogen production within Laos. The analysis of hydropower production was carried out with data provided by the government for the purpose of this study. Capacity factors for each hydropower plant were already available for previous studies of Vignesh Sridharan.

This research employed the GeoH2 model, substantially advancing the pre-processing and optimization procedures. The output and parameter values were converted from EUR to USD, sources were updated to more contemporary data, and modifications were made to tailor the model specifically for Laos. This data set can be used for further research on Laos or for a comparative analysis of other countries if results need to be reported in USD.

For preprocessing, an optimised buffer algorithm for a complete hexagon coverage was added; an addition to the SPIDER repository (Chapter 3.1.1). During the evaluation of the results, a large inconsistency was found and fixed within the model. The placement of solar and wind was done without reference to the rated power of the solar panel and the wind turbine. When the maximum available solar and wind capacity was entered in PyPSA this was done on a unit basis and not converted to MW. Furthermore, the exclusion of areas was extended by slope-based exclusion, which is relevant for Laos and its mountain topography, but also generically applicable to other countries (Chapter 3.1.2). Both additions are integrated within the normal flow of the model in the GeoH2-data-prep repository.

The main development was the incorporation of hydropower as an additional renewable energy resource within GeoH2. This was tailored to Laos, but is also applicable for other countries if a list of location and hydropower capacity is given as input. The methodology for calculating the hydraulic head is unique in this context, as it specifically computes the head for pre-existing hydropower sites. Public hydropower data frequently omits information regarding the hydraulic head, thereby complicating the analysis when using runoff data. The integration of grid capacity was already started by Müller, Leonard, Trotter, *et al.* [42] and advanced in this analysis. Due to the numerous assumptions regarding the future expansion of the Laos grid network and the necessary grid expansion capacity for new hydropower sites, this aspect of the research remains in its early stage.

Consequently, these enhancements have considerably improved the GeoH2 model, enhancing its robustness and credibility. This study exhibits significant practical applicability using real-world locations, capacities, and authentic capacity factors of hydropower plants. In addition, the results are accessible as HTML files, which simplifies usage by government officials and researchers.

5.4 Limitations and Future Work

The analysis of solar power also revealed a major flaw of the GeoH2 model, because instead of building BESS, it tended to install a higher capacity of electrolyzer or hydrogen storage. Taking the previous assumption on the hydrogen output for a 10-MW electrolyzer, an electrolyzer capacity between 41-43 MW is needed to satisfy the 2022 hydrogen demand of 6,492 tons, under

the assumption that it is continuously running at full capacity. However, the installed electrolyzer capacity is 191 MW, resulting in an average load factor of 21.5-22.5%. The average solar capacity of the defined solar hexagons is 390 MW. This is not cost-effective and, with most electrolyzers, also not feasible. This could work with Alkaline Water Electrolysis, which can go down to 20% [127]. Proton exchange membrane electrolysis can even reach around 5% [128]. However, such a low average load factor indicates that it is frequently shutdown, since it is reliant on solar power, every day. This shutdown is a lengthy process that involves depressurisation and is typically not done that frequently [129]. For hydroelectric hexagons, the electrolyser capacity is more within the calculated range, approximately 60 MW; a load factor around 70%. Furthermore, the large capacity of hydrogen storage installed in this model is unfeasible [121]. 113 tons of compressed hydrogen storage has not been installed to date. This phenomenon is also traceable to the split of annual demand into hours. Each hour is characterised by a predetermined hydrogen demand that must be satisfied. This constraint restricts the essential flexibility required for the integration of renewable energy sources, consequently inflating the cost of hydrogen. Allowing the flexibility of the hourly demand within a predefined range would bring a huge benefit to the model. This is computationally expensive, but would result in more realistic costs and taking advantage of renewable energy sources.

The Climate Impact scenario revealed a substantial difference between the results produced by Atlite and the real capacity factors. This discrepancy requires an additional analysis as the theoretical values of Atlite should align more closely with the actual conditions. This observation is also applicable to the elasticity between dry and wet years, since only two years were modelled in the study. To determine a more reliable value, it is necessary to incorporate data from additional years. Furthermore, an analysis of the total ratio and the domestic ratio, described in Table 1, revealed very small to non-existing differences. This was not expected and requires further research. During the analysis of the results, it was found that the total costs are in \$/kg for hydrogen, although the values were supposed to be displayed in \$ per kg or ton of ammonia, which was entered as the final demand state. This represents an additional error within the GeoH2 system that must be resolved for subsequent research involving other demand states, such as ammonia and urea. Originally, the objective was to provide values for ammonia and urea, but this objective was hindered by this issue. Lastly, a deeper understanding of the geospatial demand for urea is required to tailor the spatial scenarios in more detail to the domestic demand.

6 Conclusion

This study has examined cost-effective hydrogen production sites in Laos with the primary objective of generating urea fertiliser to satisfy domestic demand. The LCOH results are also applicable for hydrogen production designated for export. The model is available on Github: <https://github.com/lukasschirren/GeoH2-Case-Study-Laos>. The GeoH2 model has been specifically adapted for the Laotian context by excluding mountainous regions from potential renewable energy areas, calculating the hydraulic head for hydropower, and incorporating hydropower as an additional energy source in the PyPSA framework. The hydropower capacity factor was integrated with the runoff data from Atlite and the actual values from MEM. As a prerequisite, local fertiliser demand was forecasted.

The results were analysed on three dimensions: temporal, spatial, and climate impact. It has been shown that hydrogen can be produced with costs as low as 2.1 \$/kg. This value remains relatively stable, as it is predominantly influenced by the cost of hydropower. In the post-2030 scenario the minimal cost decreased by only 10% in comparison to the 2022 scenario. It is essential to acknowledge that within this model, the LCOH is responsive to increased demand, as evidenced by the comparison of temporal and spatial scenarios. For hydrogen production below LCOH of 3 \$/kg an upper limit was identified for each year. For 2022, the production limit is approximately 300,000 tons, increasing to 330,000 tons by 2025, 587,000 tons by 2030, and approaching 1 million tons beyond 2030. The spatial analysis revealed that the southern region is expected to become more advantageous for hydrogen production in the future due to the reduction of solar CAPEX.

Based on these findings, it is evident that hydrogen production in Laos is highly attractive and should mainly be carried out using hydropower. However, increased fluctuations in runoff as a result of climate change can have substantial effects on LCOH and can significantly restrict the advantages of hydropower. A 1% decrease in the capacity factor can result in an overproportional change in LCOH.

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A Hydrogen Production

Examples of thermochemical processes include natural gas reforming, pyrolysis, and biomass gasification. Natural gas reforming, also called SMR, is the most common hydrogen process. In the US, 95% of the hydrogen production is based on it alone [3]. The first step of the process is the steam-methane reform reaction

, and consequently CO is transformed with steam, called the water-gas shift reaction, to produce more hydrogen

, resulting in $4H_2$ [130]. This is done under pressure, which creates the required heat in the process [131].

Another thermochemical process is biomass gasification or pyrolysis. This can be considered green if biomass is considered part of a life cycle [131]. Pyrolysis converts biomass, air, and water at high temperatures into carbon monoxide, carbon dioxide, and hydrogen. The first step transforms biomass

and is followed by the water-gas shift reaction.

The electrolysis process involves the breakdown of water molecules into hydrogen and oxygen [132]. This can be done, for example, with PEM electrolysis, visible in Figure 50. Here, the anode reaction is

while the cathode reaction is

resulting in the overall process equation of

requiring electricity for the transformation [132]. Emerging topics are not considered in this paper due to uncertainty of costs and scalability [130], [131].

Figure 50: Illustration of PEM electrolysis [132]

B Data Tables

These parameters are the input for the GeoH2 model, and the tables are structured according to the actual csv files in the GitHub repository. For a different structure, even though it contains different values, the original paper from Halloran, Leonard, Salmon, *et al.* [39] can be used. The values originally in euros are indicated by an asterisk (*) and have been converted to USD using the mean exchange rate for the year 2022, which is 1.0538 [133].

B.1 Forecasted Urea Demand

	2022	2025	2030
Forecasted Fertiliser Quantity (tons)	64,923	68,234	74,114

Table 8: Forecasted urea demand values

B.2 Country Specific Parameters

Country	Laos	Source
Electricity price (USD/kWh)	0.06	Ministry of Energy and Mines (MEM), Laos
Heat price (USD/kWh)	0.028	[5]
Solar interest rate	0.075	[134]
Solar lifetime (years)	20	[135]
Wind interest rate	0.075	[134]
Wind lifetime (years)	20	[135]
Hydro interest rate	0.10	MEM, Laos
Hydro lifetime (years)	80	[136]
Plant interest rate	0.075	[134]
Plant lifetime (years)	20	[135]
Infrastructure interest rate	0.075	[134]
Infrastructure lifetime (years)	40	[137]

Table 9: Country specific parameters

Parameter	Values	Source
Electricity demand (kWh per kg H ₂)	0.35	[140]
Heat demand (kWh per kg H ₂)	0	[141]
Capex coefficient (USD per kilograms H ₂ per year)* - today	0.889	[42]
Opex (% of capex)	0.04	[142]
Hydrogenation lifetime (a)	25	[142]
Carrier costs (USD per kg carrier)*	2.116	[143]
Carrier ratio (kg carrier: kg hydrogen)	16.1	[142]

Table 12: Conversion parameters for LOHC hydrogenation

B.3 Conversion Parameters

Parameter	Values	Source
Heat capacity	0.039444	[42]
Input temperature (K)	298.15	[42]
Input pressure (bar)	25	[42]
Isentropic exponent	1.402	[42]
Isentropic efficiency	0.8	[42]
Compressor lifetime (a)	15	[138]
Compressor capex coefficient (USD per kilograms H ₂ per day)*	42189	[138]
Compressor opex (% capex)	0.04	[138]

Table 10: Conversion parameters for compression

Parameter	Values	Source
Electricity demand (kWh per kg H ₂)	13.6	[139]
Capex quadratic coefficient (USD (kg H ₂)-2)	-0.0002	[42]
Capex linear coefficient (USD per kg H ₂)*	1877.8	[42]
Capex constant (USD)*	317400000	[42]
Opex (% of capex)	0.08	[138]
Plant lifetime (a)	20	[138]

Table 11: Conversion parameters for liquid hydrogen

Parameter	Values	Source
Electricity demand (kWh per kg H ₂)	0.35	[140]
Heat demand (kWh per kg H ₂)	12	[141]
Capex coefficient (USD per kilograms H ₂ per year)*	2.59	[42]
Opex (% of capex)	0.04	[142]
Hydrogenation lifetime (a)	25	[142]

Table 13: Conversion parameters for LOHC dehydrogenation

Parameter	Values	Source
Electricity demand (kWh per kg H ₂)	2.809	[144]
Heat demand (kWh per kg H ₂)	0	-
Capex coefficient (USD per annual g H ₂)*	0.797906	[144]
Opex (% of capex)	0.015	[142]
Plant lifetime (a)	25	[142]

Table 14: Conversion parameters for ammonia synthesis

Parameter	Values	Source
Electricity demand (kWh per kg H ₂)	0	-
Heat demand (kWh per kg H ₂)	4.2	[140]
Capex coefficient (USD per hourly g H ₂)*	18191170	[145]
Opex (% of capex)	0.02	Conservative estimate
Plant lifetime (a)	25	Conservative estimate

Table 15: Conversion parameters for ammonia cracking

B.4 Conversion Transport Parameters

B.4.1 Truck

Parameter	Values	Source
Average truck speed (km/h)	40	[146]
Working hours (h/day)	24	-
Diesel price (USD/L)	0.97	[102]
Costs for driver (USD/h)	1.067	[147] (Based on annual salary and 8 hour, 5 day week)
Working days (per year)	365	-
Max driving distance (km/a)	160000	[148]
Spec capex truck (USD)*	168608	[142]
Spec opex truck (% of capex/a)	0.12	[142]
Diesel consumption (L/100 km)	35	[42]
Truck lifetime (a)	8	[142]
Trailer lifetime (a)	12	[142], [148]

Table 16: Hydrogen transportation general parameters for trucking

Parameter	Values	Source
Spec capex trailer (USD)*	695508	[138]
Spec opex trailer (% of capex/a)	0.02	[138]
Net capacity (kg H ₂)	1100	[138]
Loading unloading time (h)	1.5	[138]

Table 17: Compression parameters for trucking

Parameter	Values	Source
Spec capex trailer (USD)*	906268	[148]
Spec opex trailer (% of capex/a)	0.02	[148]
Net capacity (kg H ₂)	4300	[148]
Loading unloading time (h)	3	[148]

Table 18: Liquid hydrogen parameters for trucking

Parameter	Values	Source
Spec capex trailer (USD)*	695508	[142]
Spec opex trailer (% of capex/a)	0.02	[148]
Net capacity (kg H ₂)	1800	[148]
Loading unloading time (h)	1.5	[148]

Table 19: LOHC parameters for trucking

Parameter	Values	Source
Spec capex trailer (USD)*	221298	[142]
Spec opex trailer (% of capex/a)	0.02	[142]
Net capacity (kg H ₂)	2600	[142]
Loading unloading time (h)	1.5	[142]

Table 20: Ammonia parameters for trucking

B.4.2 Pipeline

Parameter	Values	Source
Opex (% of capex)	0.0125	[42]
Availability	0.95	[42]
Pipeline lifetime (a)	42.5	[42]
Compressor lifetime (a)	24	[42]
Electricity demand (kWh/kg*km)	0.000614	[42]
Large pipeline max capacity (GW)	13	-
Medium pipeline max capacity (GW)	4.7	-
Small pipeline max capacity (GW)	1.2	-

Table 21: Hydrogen transportation general parameters for pipeline

Parameter	Values	Source
Pipeline capex (USD)*	2950640	[149]
Compressor capex (USD)*	653356	[149]
Maximum capacity (GW)	13	[149]

Table 22: Hydrogen transportation general for pipeline (Large)

Parameter	Values	Source
Pipeline capex (USD)*	2318360	[149]
Compressor capex (USD)*	326678	[149]
Maximum capacity (GW)	4.2	[149]

Table 23: Hydrogen transportation general for pipeline (Medium)

Parameter	Values	Source
Pipeline capex (USD)*	94842	[149]
Compressor capex (USD)*	94842	[149]
Maximum capacity (GW)	1.2	[149]

Table 24: Hydrogen transportation general for pipeline (Small)

B.5 Technology Parameters

B.5.1 Hydrogen Plant

Parameter	Values	Source
CAPEX (USD/kW)	600	[150]
CAPEX (USD/kW) - 2030	450	DEEP Strategy [151], [152] (for alkaline plants above 100MW)
CAPEX (USD/kW) - 2030 onwards	320 - 400	[153]
OPEX (% of CAPEX)	0.1	[154]
Efficiency	0.59	[155]

Table 25: Parameters for Electrolyzer

Parameter	Values	Source
CAPEX (USD/MW)*	22867	[42]

Table 26: Parameters for Compressed Hydrogen Storage

B.5.2 Electricity Generation

Parameter	2022	2025	2030	2035	2040	2050	Source
Wind CAPEX (USD/kW)	1730.53	1730.53	1476.72	1476.72	1476.72	1162.92	MEM
Solar CAPEX (USD/kW)	1018	912	734	681	629	524	MEM
Hydro CAPEX (USD/kW)	2327.92	2327.92	2327.92	2327.92	2327.92	2327.92	MEM
BESS-4H CAPEX (USD/kW)	1050	800	650	625	575	500	[156]

Table 27: Parameters for Electricity generation

B.5.3 Water

Parameter	Values	Source
Freshwater treatment electricity demand (kWh/m ³)	0.4	[157]
Ocean water treatment electricity demand (kWh/m ³)	3.7	[158]
Water transport cost (USD/100 km/m ³)	0.06	[159]
Water specific cost (USD/m ³)	0.247	[160]
Water demand (L/kg H ₂)	24	[161]

Table 28: Parameters for water usage and costs

B.5.4 Infrastructure Parameters

Parameter	Values	Source
Short Road CAPEX (USD/km)	515563	[162]
Road OPEX (% of Capex)	0.1	[162]

Table 29: Parameters for road construction

C Model Running Improvements

Attempts to run the model in parallel frequently resulted in inconsistent values. Nevertheless, as the model has an execution time of eight hours, an efficient way to run models was necessary. An improvement involved initiating the subsequent run immediately upon completion of the previous model run. This was achieved through process identification (PID) of the :

```
import time
import subprocess
import psutil

target_pid = 12064 // PID of current model run

def is_process_running(pid):
    return psutil.pid_exists(pid)
def run_script(script_name):
    subprocess.run(["python", script_name])

print(f"Waiting for process with PID {target_pid} to complete...")
while is_process_running(target_pid):
    time.sleep(300) // Check every 5 minutes

print(f"Process with PID {target_pid} has completed. Starting the scripts...\n")

run_script("assign_country_2.py")
run_script("optimize_transport_and_conversion_2.py")
run_script("optimize_hydrogen_plant_temporal_2.py")
```

D Temporal Scenario Figures

D.1 2022

Figure 51: Temporal scenarios - visualisaion of minimum hexagon based on LCOH.

Figure 52: 2022 scenario spatial visualisaion of minimum hexagon based on total cost

Figure 53: 2022 scenario spatial visualisaion of minimum hexagon based on LCOH

Figure 54: 2022 trucking scenario minimal LCOH hexagon split by components.

Figure 55: 2022 trucking scenario minimal LCOH hexagon compared to the average.

D.2 2025

Figure 56: Scenario 2025 lowest cost hexagon map

Figure 57: 2025 scenario spatial visualisation of minimum hexagon based on total cost

(a) Installed hydropower capacity

(b) Installed solar capacity

Figure 59: Scenario 2025 installed capacity of (a) hydropower and (b) solar energy per hexagon

(a) LCOH cost - trucking

(b) LCOH cost -pipeline

Figure 58: 2025 scenario spatial visualisation of minimum hexagon based on LCOH

Figure 60: Scenario 2025 installed wind capacity per hexagon

Figure 61: 2025 Visualisation of top 100 hexagons based on lowest LCOH values.

Figure 62: 2025 Scenario Boxplot of average total costs splitted by pipeline and trucking across different hexagon categories: (1) with hydropower above zero, (2) with solar above zero and without hydro and wind, (3) with wind and without hydro and solar.

Figure 63: 2025 trucking scenario minimal LCOH hexagon split by components.

Figure 64: 2025 trucking scenario minimal LCOH hexagon compared to the average.

D.3 2030

Figure 65: Scenario 2030 lowest cost hexagon map

Figure 66: 2030 scenario spatial visualisaion of minimum hexagon based on total cost

Figure 67: 2030 scenario spatial visualisaion of minimum hexagon based on LCOH

(a) Installed hydropower capacity

(b) Installed solar capacity

Figure 68: Scenario 2030 installed capacity of (a) hydropower and (b) solar energy per hexagon

Figure 69: Scenario 2030 installed wind capacity per hexagon

Figure 71: 2030 Scenario Boxplot of average total costs splitted by pipeline and trucking across different hexagon categories: (1) with hydropower above zero, (2) with solar above zero and without hydro and wind, (3) with wind and without hydro and solar.

Figure 70: 2030 Visualisation of top 100 hexagons based on lowest LCOH values.

Figure 72: 2030 trucking scenario minimal LCOH hexagon split by components.

Figure 73: 2030 trucking scenario minimal LCOH hexagon compared to the average.

D.4 Post-2030

Figure 74: Scenario post-2030 lowest cost hexagon map

Figure 75: Post-2030 scenario spatial visualisation of minimum hexagon based on total cost

(a) Installed hydropower capacity

(b) Installed solar capacity

Figure 77: Scenario post-2030 installed capacity of (a) hydropower and (b) solar energy per hexagon

(a) LCOH cost - trucking

(b) LCOH cost - pipeline

Figure 76: Post-2030 scenario spatial visualisation of minimum hexagon based on LCOH

Figure 78: Scenario post-2030 installed wind capacity per hexagon

Figure 79: Post-2030 Visualisation of top 100 hexagons based on lowest LCOH values.

Figure 80: Post-2030 Scenario Boxplot of average total costs splitted by pipeline and trucking across different hexagon categories: (1) with hydropower above zero, (2) with solar above zero and without hydro and wind, (3) with wind and without hydro and solar.

Figure 81: Post-2030 trucking scenario minimal LCOH hexagon split by components.

Figure 82: Post-2030 trucking scenario minimal LCOH hexagon compared to the average.

E Spatial Scenario Figures

Region	Cost Type	Min Cost (\$/kg)	Avg Cost (\$/kg)
Northern	Pipeline LCOH Cost	2.10	7.62
	Pipeline Total Cost	2.70	14.66
	Trucking LCOH Cost	2.38	7.79
	Trucking Total Cost	2.74	8.34
Central	Pipeline LCOH Cost	2.31	11.12
	Pipeline Total Cost	3.15	15.65
	Trucking LCOH Cost	2.54	11.27
	Trucking Total Cost	2.89	11.74
Southern	Pipeline LCOH Cost	2.31	11.11
	Pipeline Total Cost	3.88	13.98
	Trucking LCOH Cost	2.43	11.22
	Trucking Total Cost	2.83	11.74

Table 30: Minimum and average LCOH and total costs over spatial dimension

Figure 83: Minimum total cost across spatial dimension

Figure 84: Minimum cost components over spatial dimension

Figure 85: Northern Scenario Boxplot of average total costs splitted by pipeline and trucking across different hexagon categories: (1) with hydropower above zero, (2) with solar above zero and without hydro and wind, (3) with wind and without hydro and solar.

Figure 86: Central Scenario Boxplot of average total costs splitted by pipeline and trucking across different hexagon categories: (1) with hydropower above zero, (2) with solar above zero and without hydro and wind, (3) with wind and without hydro and solar.

Figure 87: Southern Scenario Boxplot of average total costs splitted by pipeline and trucking across different hexagon categories: (1) with hydropower above zero, (2) with solar above zero and without hydro and wind, (3) with wind and without hydro and solar.

F Climate Impact Scenario Figures

(a) 2019 LCOH hexagon map

(b) 2022 LCOH hexagon map

Figure 88: Climate Impact Scenario (a) 2019 and (b) 2022 LCOH hexagon maps

Figure 89: Violin chart of hydropower hexagons total cost for 2019 and 2021

Year	Min Pipeline	Avg Pipeline	Min Trucking	Avg Trucking
2019	7.77 \$/kg	11.36 \$/kg	7.85 \$/kg	11.43 \$/kg
2022	2.67 \$/kg	11.34 \$/kg	2.76 \$/kg	11.41 \$/kg

Table 31: LCOH comparison of pipeline and trucking between 2019 and 2022

Year	Min Pipeline	Avg Pipeline	Min Trucking	Avg Trucking
2019	8.64 \$/kg	12.70 \$/kg	8.21 \$/kg	11.85 \$/kg
2022	4.94 \$/kg	12.69 \$/kg	3.29 \$/kg	11.83 \$/kg

Table 32: Total cost comparison of pipeline and trucking between 2019 and 2022

Year	Min Pipeline	Avg Pipeline	Min Trucking	Avg Trucking
2019	7.77 \$/kg	10.21 \$/kg	7.85 \$/kg	10.29 \$/kg
2022	2.67 \$/kg	10.07 \$/kg	2.76 \$/kg	10.16 \$/kg

Table 33: LCOH comparison of hydropower hexagons pipeline and trucking between 2019 and 2022

Year	Min Pipeline	Avg Pipeline	Min Trucking	Avg Trucking
2019	8.64 \$/kg	11.50 \$/kg	8.21 \$/kg	10.71 \$/kg
2022	4.94 \$/kg	11.43 \$/kg	3.29 \$/kg	10.59 \$/kg

Table 34: Total cost comparison of hydropower hexagons pipeline and trucking between 2019 and 2022

Figure 90: Climate Impact 2019 trucking scenario minimal LCOH hexagon split by components

Figure 91: Climate Impact 2019 pipeline scenario minimal LCOH hexagon split by components

	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec
Donesahong	161.1	146.3	175.8	180.0	194.0	191.0	196.7	193.6	182.3	194.0	184.1	183.0

Table 35: Don Sahong Dam production in 2022 in GWh

Figure 92: Climate Impact 2022 trucking scenario minimal LCOH hexagon split by components

Figure 93: Climate Impact 2022 pipeline scenario minimal LCOH hexagon split by components

Figure 94: Change of cost components between 2019 and 2022 trucking scenario

Figure 95: Relationship between capacity factor and costs for 2019 and 2022